

International Journal of Educational Studies and Policy (IJESP)

Volume: 4, Issue: 2, November 2023

“He is like Mevlâna!, She is an Amazon Warrior!”: Reflection on Successful School Leadership in Socioeconomically Disadvantaged Contexts through Metaphors

Ali Duran¹, Necati Cemaloğlu²

ABSTRACT

The notions of successful school principalship and how to get things done effectively in schools are often argued about, but not definitely agreed upon, by educational researchers, policy makers, practitioners. This study was to contribute to the literature on what it means with successful school principalship, by analyzing the metaphorical perceptions of a vast array of participants (deputies, teachers, students, and parents) from a broad area of schools. Designed as qualitative research, this inquiry is an ethnomethodological attempt. The data were obtained through individual or focus-group interviews through a semi-structured interview form. The metaphorical analyses rest upon the interpretive content analysis that enabled us to conduct in-depth analyses of metaphors so that we could make inferences about the professional identity of the successful school principalship. The metaphors are analyzed in a school leadership framework. This analysis contributes to the ongoing endeavour on seeking for successful principals' characteristics, attitudes, and behaviors. Metaphors revealed in this study have shown that the successful school principals in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts often display paternalistic, transformational, moral and servant leadership behaviors. The participants depicted affectionate, self-sacrificing, caring, disciplined, innovative and benevolent portrait of school principals. Several recommendations and implications for policy, research and practitioners are offered.

Keywords: Successful school principals, metaphor, paternalistic leadership, socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10160091>

Article Info:

Received: 04.03.2023

Accepted: 16.11.2023

Article Type: Research Article

Cite as: Duran, A. & Cemaloğlu, N. (2023). “He is like Mevlâna!, She is an Amazon Warrior!”: Reflection on successful school leadership in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts through metaphors. *International Journal of Educational Studies and Policy*, 4(2), 91-128.

¹Corresponding Author: Dr. Ali Duran, Ministry of National Education, aliduranedu@hotmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0001-6132-4066

²Prof. Dr. Necati Cemaloğlu, Gazi University, necem@gazi.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0001-7753-2222

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Introduction

“Education is a deeply mysterious process and so is the business of being a leader” Greenfield (1984, p.167).

The issue of successful educational leadership in schools is of great interest among researchers in educational administration, policy makers, and practitioners. Therefore, among the basic focuses of the school effectiveness research (Bipath & Moyo, 2016; Brookover et al., 1982; Edmonds, 1979; Frederickson & Edmonds, 1979; Lezotte, 1986) are the characteristics (Holly, 2009), attitudes (Wong & Law, 2017), behaviors (Johnson, 2005), roles (Reid, 2020), responsibilities (Fullwood, 2016) and practices (Alqahtani, Noman & Kaur, 2020) of successful school principals, who have been proved to play a key role in a school context (Engels et al. 2008, p.160), and are regarded as “change agents” or “culture builders” (Leo & Wickenberg (2013, p. 407). There is evidence to suggest that culture begins with leadership (Giancola & Hutchison, 2005). Further, culture is the result of a group’s accumulated learning the culture itself will later define the required leadership (Kaul, 2015, p. 304).

Studies on successful school principals are one of the most common research lines in recent decades (Day, 2007; Drysdale & Gurr, 2011; Santaella, 2018). Previous research has led scholars to gather behind the idea that successful school leadership is second only to effective classroom teaching in its impact on student achievement (Bush & Glover, 2014). Drysdale and Gurr (2011) draw attention to the fact that school leadership continues to appeal a renewed attention in terms of its impact on student performance. This is so much so that, findings across the world demonstrated that school leadership is a crucial factor on student achievement (Hallinger & Heck, 1996; Leithwood, Louis, Anderson, & Wahlstrom, 2004). There have even been released of evidence, which show that successful school leadership accounts for as much as one quarter of the in-school difference in student achievement (Nichols, Glass, & Berliner, 2012).

Based on an extensive examination of literature on school principalship, it is seen that among the scientific endeavors to define school leadership in school contexts are metaphorical analysis regarding school principals. Through metaphors, much about how school principals interpret their professional identity in their organizations can be revealed no matter how they emerge, verbally or symbolically (Bredeson, 1987). From this point of view, it can be noted that metaphors can be employed to be able to understand the nature of school principalship in terms of characteristics and behaviors as well as roles and responsibilities. In this sense, past research has revealed the use of a great number of metaphors of school principal. It can be said that most of these metaphors are attempts to clarify the nature of the school principalship (Inbar, 1996).

The literature, on the other hand, includes a great deal of research on metaphors about school principals, but the research in metaphorical analysis of successful school principals remains limited. Only a few scholars have focused on this topic (Parylo & Zepeda, 2014; Trnavčević, & Roncelli Vaupot, 2009). More recent evidence on metaphors and school leadership comes from several studies (Heffernan, 2019; Heffernan, Netolicky & Mockler, 2019; Maguire & Braun, 2019; Meyer & Patuawa, 2020). In this sense, Heffernan (2019) advanced a new metaphor, called “the punk rock principal”, which refers to a school leader who thinks outside the box, and takes new approaches, changing traditional way of power and structures for school vision. In this metaphor, a school leader positions the school principalship behind the scenes instead of being visible at the front, leading us to reconsider the traditional school leadership approaches (Heffernan, 2019).

Much has been said of the metaphors on school principals, but too little has been said of what successful school leaders look like in the minds of teachers, deputies, students, or parents. “Metaphors need to be discussed in the contexts from which they come rather than presented as universally applicable” (Samier, 2019, p. 192). In this sense, no research has been obtained about the metaphorical images on successful school principalship in Türkiye. At this precise point, an important question emerges as follow: Can metaphors be employed to figure out what being a successful school principal means in Turkish context? Would there be similarities or differences when compared to other contexts in different parts or cultures across the world?

Successful school principalship, on the other hand, is likely to be even more crucial in low-performing schools, in which successful school principals seem to have significantly effects (Leithwood, Louis, Anderson & Wahlstrom, 2004) as well as in schools located socio-economically disadvantaged areas (Llorent-Bedmar, Cobano-Delgado, & Navarro-Granados, 2019; Moral, Martín-Romera, Martínez-Valdivia, & Olmo-Extremera, 2018) or in schools with students from disadvantaged backgrounds (Naidoo & Perumal, 2014; Santaella, 2018). There has been growing interest the traits, qualities, and applications of school principals who can make difference in schools with failures and are able to turn the things reverse. However, surprisingly little attention has been paid to delve into the identities of turnaround school principals (Meyers & Hitt, 2017).

The previous research has shown that successful school leadership is contextual in its nature, so the context is everything (Day, Gu & Sammons, 2016). Another evidence emerging from the literature is that successful school principals put their efforts and try to do what they can and must do to promote effective instruction, but their actions aren't displayed by the perfect replication of recipes. Instead, school principals, even in the same geopolitical contexts, vary in their routes to success by their context-based leadership practices (Noman, Hashim & Abdullah, 2018). Recognizing the distinctive challenges faced by schools in socioeconomically disadvantaged areas, it becomes imperative to understand how leadership styles and strategies adapt in these contexts. In regions marked by economic hardships, limited resources, and social challenges, the role of a school principal transcends beyond mere administrative duties. The need for empathy, resilience, and innovative problem-solving is amplified in these environments. Research indicates that in such settings, successful school principals often act not just as educational leaders, but as community leaders too, fostering a sense of hope and striving to overcome barriers to student success. They play a pivotal role in not only improving educational outcomes but also in enhancing the overall well-being of students and their families. Consequently, exploring the metaphorical perceptions of what constitutes successful principalship in these challenging environments becomes not only relevant but essential for a comprehensive understanding of successful school leadership. Accordingly, it would be logical to investigate the metaphorical perceptions of the main stakeholders; teachers, deputies, students, and parents as to what being a successful school principal is, and even how successful school principals act in socio-economically disadvantaged contexts. As noted above, despite having been investigated for more than a century, there has been still no consensus about the personal qualities, skills, and abilities of successful school principalship (Parylo & Zepeda, 2014). Grint (2005) (1992) suggests that successful school principals don't have the same qualities or don't display the same actions in each context or culture. Instead, these outliers embrace their contexts, and act accordingly to launch into new adventure of school leadership. The focus of this study is to delve into the professional identities of successful school principals in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts in a broad research site.

Contribution to the Literature

The phenomenon of successful leadership, on the other hand, has been researched worldwide, using qualitative designs and methodologies. However, very few, if any, qualitative inquiries have been conducted in Turkish context. Accordingly, this study is expected to fill the void in the literature on both successful school principalship and metaphorical perceptions about them by explicating the cognitive reflections of teachers, deputies, students, and parents on successful school principals in disadvantaged contexts. This study differs from the available literature in metaphorical perceptions of school principals in that we address the issue from the perspectives both successful school principalship and being successful in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts. Another contribution of this study is the participants and its research site. In this sense, an examination of literature has revealed no study in which teachers, deputies, students, and parents were recruited. Further, the research site is the four cities in Türkiye. Further, a few studies (e.g., Hernández-Amorós, & Martínez-Ruiz, 2018) examined the metaphors in terms of contemporary leadership styles has been found in the literature, so this study will be expected to contribute and to provide a new insight into the metaphorical analysis on leadership styles. Therefore, this study is thought to bring a new route to the metaphorical analyses on school principalship.

Purpose of the Research

In this sense, the main purpose of this study was to focus on the metaphorical perceptions of the main stakeholders, teachers, deputies, students, and parents in arenas of school administration. Within the framework of this main research problem, these questions guided this study:

- (a) What are the metaphorical perceptions of teachers, deputies, students, and parents on successful school principals?
- (b) What are the school leadership styles displayed by successful school principals in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts?

A Review of the Literature

School Principalship in Türkiye

During the first years of Turkish Republic, John Dewey made some suggestions related to selecting and training school administrators in his report in 1924, but there hasn't been a well-established and continuous practice from that time (Cemaloğlu, 2005). When we examine the archive of Official Gazette in Türkiye from 1970 and 2018, there have been 16 legislative regulations on recruitment of school administrators, and almost half of them have been issued during the last decade. On the other hand, some amendments were made in the scope of the Regulation on the Amendment of the Regulation on the Assignment of School Administrators to the Educational Institutions of the Ministry of National Education in the Official Gazette numbered 30681 dated February 9, 2019. In line with this regulation, school principals are supposed to enter a 150-minute exam which includes 80 multiple-choice questions that include general ability, general culture, Atatürk's principles and revolutionary history, values education, ethics in education and training, education sciences and legislation. The candidates who will apply for the exam must be teachers in the Ministry of National Education. Those who intend to be assigned as deputies must also enter this exam. Following the exam, the candidates are supposed to attend interview sessions. Additionally, the candidates take extra scores from their background studies, experience years, prizes, etc. Finally, the scores of the written exam, the interviews, and the

previous background are calculated and a sum of the score is formed. This final score is used to assign them according to their choices from the vacant positions in the province. All school principals in state school in Türkiye work for government and have teaching background.

What Counts as Successful School Principalship?

The greatest contribution to the literature comes from the International Successful School Principalship Project (ISSPP) (Drysdale, 2011; Murakami, & Orr, 2012), which is the most comprehensive and coherent international comparative study of the principalship ever undertake (Day, 2015), and encompasses a diverse list of countries from different continents as follows: America (Brazil, Canada, Chile, Mexico, USA, and Puerto Rico), Europe (Austria, Cyprus, Finland, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Türkiye, and UK), Africa (South Africa and Kenya), Asia (China, Israel, New Zealand, and Singapore), and Australia. At this precise point, it is imperative to mention that the incentive and evidence for us to conduct this study to seek for outlier principals in Turkish context comes from the ISSPP even if the present study is not a part of this huge collaborative research team.

If we are to refer some evidence from the ISSPP, having examined thirteen schools from the USA, Australia, and England, Ylimaki, Jacobson and Drysdale (2007) have concluded that the improvement in each school can be attributed to the school principal personality, attitude and behaviors, namely effective school leadership. In another study as a part of the ISSPP, an updated model of successful school leadership based on Australian case studies, it was concluded that much of the student achievement and school improvement was attributed to the educational leadership (Drysdale & Gurr, 2011). The basic outcomes of the ISSPP research on successful school leadership practices from Australia, New Zealand, United States of America, China, Denmark, Norway, Sweden and United Kingdom were classified into five categories: (1) setting directions, building a vision and maintaining high expectations; (2) developing people, obtaining their trust and support, and expanding their capacity; (3) redesigning the organization to distribute leadership in a safe and collaborative environment; (4) managing instructional programs through productive forms of faculty engagement and providing needed resources; and (5) coalition building with internal and external stakeholders (Day & Leithwood, 2007).

Despite the limited number and scope, there are also studies from Türkiye. Along with the article by Ağaoğlu, Şimşek, Ceylan & Kesim (2012) on the characteristics of successful Turkish principals within the scope of the ISSPP, only a few scholars have followed this path into the successful school principalship in terms of the traits of effective school principals (Gürbüz, Erdem & Yıldırım, 2013; Karahasanoğlu, 2014), motivation strategies of successful principals (Elçi & Tan, 2015), and the leadership practices of successful school principals (Kızıldeniz, 2017). In the study by Ağaoğlu, Şimşek, Ceylan and Kesim (2012), it was concluded that successful school principals attached priority to building a trust of culture and leading the school members to involve in decision-making processes, especially while focusing on the innovative practices. The researchers also found evidence several roles displayed by the school principals: leadership, fatherhood, friendship and fraternity, mentorship, source of knowledge, and facilitator. Being respected by the school community and using “we” language, the successful school principals were found to provide effective feedback to teachers about their works and were considered as transformational leaders in their organizations (Ağaoğlu, Şimşek, Ceylan & Kesim, 2012).

Metaphors on School Principals

An extensive examination of the literature has revealed that school principals are also one of the trend themes of metaphorical analysis. When we consider the importance of school principals for a school context, especially in centred and bureaucratic structures like in Türkiye, it is not a surprising issue as the authority is held by the school principals. In this sense, Beck and Murphy (1993) conducted an extensive research on metaphors related to school principals and presented their findings in decades in terms of the dominant metaphors: School Principal as Values Broker (1920s), School Principal as Scientific Manager (1930s), School Principal as Democratic Manager (1940s), School Principal as Theory-Guided Administrator (1950s), School Principal as Bureaucratic Executive (1960s), School Principal as Humanistic Facilitator (1970s), School Principal as Instructional Leader (1980s), School Principal as Leader, Servant, Organizational Architect, Social Architect, Educator, Moral Agent, and Person in the Community (1990s). Cerit (2008) examined the metaphorical perceptions of teachers and elementary students on the school principals and found that director, leader, researcher, supervisor, and counsellor are the most repeated metaphors. In another one, more fresh evidence comes from Ozgenel and Gokce (2019) who investigated the primary students' metaphorical perceptions related to school principals and found that leader, director, family, teacher, and hardworking are the most repeated codes. Hernández-Amorós and Martínez Ruiz (2018) found such metaphors as counsellor, coordinator and facilitator, a tourist guide, or a train locomotive, whereas Yalçın and Erginer (2012) concluded family leader, father, locomotive, orchestra conductor and brain, angle, lion. Table 1 summarizes the main findings of the previous research on focusing the metaphorical perceptions on school principals.

Table 1. Metaphors on school principals elicited by previous literature

Researcher(S)	Main findings
Akan, Yalçın and Yıldırım (2014)	commander, soldier, administrator, orchestra conductor, and organization leaders
Akın-Kösterelioğlu (2014)	father, machine gear, mother, locomotive, and sun
Akyol and Kapçak (2017)	captain, gardener, father, dictator, and shepherd
Allen (2004)	protective buffers, cheerleaders, caretakers and mother hens, listeners, coaches, balancers
Argyropoulou and Hatira (2014)	donkey, horse, cat, tightrope walker, forest, ship
Aydoğdu, 2008	boss, parent, ship captain, mirror, officer, angle, computer, and flower
Bredeson (1987)	maintenance, survival and vision.
Çobanoğlu and Gökcalp (2015)	father, lion, mother, dictator, and shepherd
Dönmez (2008)	parent, the head of the family, candle, orchestra conductor, umbrella, queen bee, tree, and lion king
Fennell (1996)	shepherd, judge, servanthood, river, and volcano
Inbar, (1996)	boss, king, super governor, super commander, roaring lion and warrior.
Kadi and Beytekin (2017)	engine of car, ferris wheel, battlefield, factory, farm, company, boat, football team, moon
Korkmaz and Çevik (2018)	football coach, ship captain, father, team captain, and brain
Linn, Sherman and Gill (2007)	mother, gardener, mountain climber, fisher, sailor on a small boat, juggler, and jigsaw puzzler
Monroe (2003)	chief executive officer, student advocate, orchestra conductor, facilitator, and mother
Ozgenel and Gökçe (2019)	leader, director, family, teacher, and hardworking
Örücü (2014)	parent, orchestra conductor, root of a tree, sculptor, commander
Parylo and Zepeda (2014)	a team player, a perfect fit, a data leader, a community leader, and a passionate leader

Pesen, Kara and Gedik, (2015)	cat, sugar, mother, dictator, and flowers
Turhan and Yaraş (2013)	referee, heart, commander, family, father, book, bee, and parents
Tüzel and Şahin, (2014)	father, president, flower, teacher, and sun
Tvnavcevic and Vaupot (2009).	mother, father, the head of the family, hen with chickens, and big dictator
Yalçın and Erginer (2014)	disciplien chief, caring, problem solver, egalitarian, and equalizer
Zembat, Tunçeli and Akşin (2015)	father, leader, mother, brain, and parent

When we interpret the results of the previous literature, it can be noted that the school principals are often considered both the most powerful individual in the school context and the most important one to protect and guide teachers and students. In Turkish context, particularly, one can see the footprints of paternalistic school principals who hold both the authority and the affection. Transformational and servant leadership are also other themes with the metaphors such as gardener, problem solver, and bee. Further, when we think all findings together, there are no huge differences regarding the metaphorical perceptions on school principals. Bush and Glover (2014) emphasize that there are artificial distinctions or ideal types among school leadership styles, and successful school leaders may embrace all of them according to context. Considering this in terms of this current research, we attempted to classify the metaphors the sharpest notions of the school leadership styles.

Past research has also revealed several negative metaphorical perceptions: visual pollution, angry bull, sharp vinegar, creaking door & broken record (Erden, 2016) and politician, commander, boss, and guardian (Örücü, 2014). Örücü (2014) concluded that the metaphorical perceptions of the teachers regarding the school principals were mostly negative, and attributed them to the perceptions on school principals, including authority, power, centralized system, resilient to change, burnout, and political behaviors.

Method

Research Model

This paper is based on ethno-phenomenological research design in order to describe the perspectives on the phenomena, we employed ethnographic approach and interpretive phenomenology as a combined methodology. These two approaches can be combined in ways that both are exploratory interviews and allow researchers to delve into meaning in the individual's experiences (Crotty, 1998).

Recruitment and Participants

Based on the research context above, a total of 231 teachers, 19 deputies, 220 students, and 133 parents who have outstanding school principals selected based on several criteria were recruited in this study. This study was conducted in four provinces, located in the Black Sea Region in Türkiye.

In this study, the reason why teachers, deputies, students, and parents were recruited can be explained via a metaphor, employed by Wildy (2003, p.120). In this metaphor, the successful school principals represent “a statue” with three faces like other 3D objects having faces, edges, and vertices, which can be likened a prism, as well. By looking at the statute from different angles, we can see its different faces, thereby providing us with different lenses to elicit meanings or interpretations of the way successful school principals lead. The three data sets were the lenses through which the statue is viewed. In our case, this array of diverse participants gave us a 3D

perspective regarding successful school principalship, thereby allowing us to make some inferences to be able to do some generalizations based on the logic of inductive probabilistic reasoning (Payne & Williams, 2005).

The steps of the recruitment participants is as follow: (1) determining the research site, (2) having official permission from the Ministry of Education, (3) listing all the schools in the research site, (4) defining the selection criteria for successful school principals, (5) determining the candidates based on the criteria with collaboration of the authorities both in the provinces and districts, (6) finalizing the list of successful school principals, (7) inviting the school principals to the study, (8) determining the stakeholders, (9) inviting the stakeholders to the study, and (10) launching the data collection.

For determining the school principals, the criterion (Creswell, 2012) and extreme group case selection (Brinkerhoff, 2003) sampling methods were employed. In this sense, researchers identified 21 school principals who (a) were working in a school with socio-economic disadvantaged context, (b) had students from socio-economic disadvantaged backgrounds, (c) displayed extraordinary success beyond the expectations in high-stakes exams, (D) remained at least 3 years in the current school, and (e) had reputation with positive outcomes, well-beings of the stakeholders, and were considered as successful in the minds of officials in the province or districts.

Since it was a difficult issue to determine the success or the effectiveness of school principals (Bartell, 1989), there were some extra considerations we paid during the selection process. We recruited the schools whose principals were outliers with their administrative, management, and leadership style (Asiedu-Kumi, 2013; Garza, Murakami-Ramalho, & Merchant, 2011), had reputation (Gu, Day, Walker, & Leithwood, 2018; Tubin, 2017), were rewarded at local and national level (Steyn, 2014), had extraordinary academic achievements given the school context (Ylimaki, Jacobson & Drysdale, 2007), had high scores in supervisions and inspections (Drysdale, Gurr, & Goode, 2016). At this precise point, it must be noted that the utmost importance was given to be able to comply with the literature while recruiting the successful school principals (Asiedu-Kumi, 2013, Balitewicz, 2015; Bennett & Murakami, 2016; Crum & Sherman, 2008; Day, 2005; De Lisle, Annisette, Bowrin-Williams, 2019; Dimmock & O'Donoghue, 1997).

Ylimaki, Jacobson & Drysdale (2007), on the other hand, highlight that the school principals who were recruited in research which focus on successful school principalship don't have to be the best ones in the region. Instead, they need to be those who have displayed extraordinary leadership attitudes and have acquired both positive outcomes in terms of student achievements and well-being of the school organization. Further, the success of these schools isn't completely attributed to the school principals. It is assumed that school principals in this study were partly accountable in the success of the school organizations with their administrative, management, and leadership styles.

A total of 603 participants (%38 teachers, %3 deputies, %37 students, and %22 parents) who have outstanding school principals selected based on several criteria were recruited in this study. When we examine the sociodemographic characteristics of study participants (Teachers N = 231, deputies' N = 19, students' N = 220, and parents' N = 133), the related information can be

listed as follows: %51 of teachers was female. Teachers' age distribution are as follows: %17 20-30, %64 31-40, %17 41-50, and %2 51 and above years old. When it comes to total experience, it can be listed as: %13 1-5, %29 6-10, %30 11-15, %19 15-20, and %9 21 and above years of experience. Teachers' working durations in the current school are as follows: %66 1-5, %29 6-10, %4 11-15, and %1 16 and above years of experience. Teachers' branch distribution can be listed as: %16 Turkish, %13 English, %13 Classroom, %13 Maths, %10 Social Science, %10 Science, %4 P.E., %4 Religion, %4 Technology and Design, %3 Preschool, %3 Counselling, %3 Music, %2 ICT, %2 Art. %21 of deputies was female. Deputies' age distribution are as follows: %5 20-30, %74 31-40, and %21 41-50. When it comes to total experience, it can be listed as: %26 6-10, %37 11-15, 16 15-20, and %21 21 and above years of experience. All deputies have 1-5 years working durations in the current school. Deputies' branch distribution can be listed as: The %65 of students were girls. The age distribution of the students are as follows: %3 10, %10 11, %17 12, %34 13, %32 14, and %4 15 years old. The students' education grades are as follows: %7 5th, %16 6th, %30 7th, and %47 8th grade students. %55 of the parents was female. %5 of them were between 20-30 years age. %51 of them were between 31-40 years age, and %44 of them were between 41-50 years age. The educational background of the parents are as follows: %26 primary, %32 secondary, %34 high school, and %8 bachelor's degrees.

Data Collection

In this study, interviews were conducted to collect data about the metaphorical perceptions of the stakeholders in socio-economically disadvantaged contexts. We conducted individual or focus-group interviews while collecting data based on the status of school organizations and timetables of the participants, as well as the researchers (Seidman, 2006). As the participants of qualitative studies experience the phenomena in the research by themselves, they can express and provide data about the research theme (Ritchie, Lewis, McNaughton & Ormston, 2014). Yin (2016), on the other hand, highlights that if data are collected through only interviews, then the obtained data will be the self-responses of the participants. Accordingly, this study is subjected to this limitation, but we attempted to include diverse participants in a larger research site to compensate this research limitation in this paper.

In choosing methods of data collection, we carefully considered the tradition of metaphor analysis research in social sciences, which is strongly rooted in educational research. There is evidence from the literature that metaphors provide an insight into the concepts and discourses that underpin the concept of principalship (Trancevic & Vaupot, 2009). Another support for metaphor analysis in favor of principalship comes from Beck and Murphy (1993) along with many others mentioned above. As in our case, metaphor analysis could be particularly useful as a technique to bring studies of cognition into studies of discourse (Todd & Harrison, 2008).

An examination of the literature metaphors on school principals and educational issues in general, it is seen that most of the researchers chose to open-ended questions like "*My school principal is like/resembles because*" despite several ones who preferred to use quantitative methods for data collection in line with the purpose of their studies. In this study, the data were collected by using two open-ended questions: in the first questions, the participants were asked to use a metaphor to describe the principalship of their school principals; and in the second question, they were asked to justify why they chose this metaphor.

Data Analysis

Previous literature shows no fixed and established ways of metaphorical analysis. There are some researchers who embrace their own approaches (e.g., Fabian, 2006), whereas many others prefer basic content analysis (Todd & Harrison, 2008). If we refer to literature in Turkish content, there are almost identical classifications while conducting the metaphorical analysis as researchers often cite previous research while doing metaphorical analysis. As a result, the conventional analysis does not provide new insights into research as much as intended. Instead, there occur similar classifications following the analysis. On the other hand, Ginger (2006) argues that researchers from different contexts look to the qualitative data as a valuable source, so there exist different analysis approaches. In our contribution, we will present a procedure for interpretive content analysis so that we could understand the underlying predispositions and assumptions of the stakeholders in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts as to what successful school principalship means. Krippendorff (2013, p. 24) conceptualizes interpretive content analysis as “a technique for valid inferences from texts to the contexts of their use.” In interpretive content analysis, however, meaning is not simply “contained” in the text (p. 25). Ahuvia (2001, p. 139) states that interpretive content analysis allows researchers to reveal latent meanings in a text. According to Krippendorff (2013), researchers can go beyond descriptive questions of “what” and “how” and continues to draw inferences about “why,” “for whom,” and “to what effect” in interpretive content analysis (p. 27).

In this study, we chose to employ interpretive content analysis technique for the analyses of metaphors in that we could make inferences about successful school leadership models in Turkish context. In this sense, we analyzed the obtained metaphors through a perspective by Reagan (2010), suggested by Berg (2008). We did so because we wanted to re-articulate the participants’ metaphors about successful school principalship.

The steps of the metaphorical analysis in this research are as follows: (a) sorting the metaphors, (b) identifying the core themes using their relative frequencies, (c) combining and consolidating codes before interpretation, (d) validity and reliability, and (e) building leadership model. It can be noted that almost for the half of the century, school leadership literature has responded the challenges, pressures, changes, innovations, and expectations with several models of school leadership (Hallinger & Heck, 2010) or some kinds of professional standards (NPBEA, 2011). Bush and Glover (2014) assert that theory is one of the four vital elements of school leadership along with policy, research, and practice to be able to provide helpful insights into how schools are led and managed (s. 556). In this sense, as a difference previous research, we used the metaphorical codes to build a leadership scheme displayed by successful school principals in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts.

In many metaphor studies, only one person identifies and analyzes the metaphors. Although this is often the most convenient way to analyze the data, it may be preferable to have a second coder for at least some of the data. The second coder could check the identification of metaphors and/or the grouping of metaphors together (Todd & Harrison, 2008). In our study, the second researcher examined the codes, and the researchers’ agreement was calculated via Miles and Huberman’s formula (1994). In qualitative coding techniques, focusing inter-rater reliability (IRR) is a useful way of ensuring the trustworthiness when multiple researchers are involved with

coding. Miles and Huberman (1994) recommend that an IRR of 80% agreement between coders on 95% of the codes is sufficient agreement among multiple coders. In this sense, the agreement between two coders were found as %94. The second coder suggested to transfer some of the metaphors to different leadership categories (e.g., from transformational leadership to visionary leadership).

Trustworthiness

Metaphor provides possibilities in the arena of school leadership scholarship, but researchers need to carefully interrogate their choices and how those influence the theorization of leadership in schools (Netolicky, 2019). In this research, trustworthiness was attempted to be ensured. Credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability were addressed (Lincoln & Guba 1985, Graneheim & Lundman, 2004). In this sense, we took several measures. First, we recruited the diverse participants from 21 different successful schools with exemplary leaders who were selected based on several certain criteria. Gender and geographical districts were also paid attention. Second, two researchers obeyed the analyzing processes mentioned above, and conducted the analysis accordingly. After the analyses by one researcher in this study, the emerging themes were discussed in detail and the agreement rate was reached. Further, Cresswell (1998) offers several domains of rigor: (1) prolonged engagement, (2) triangulation, (3) rich, thick description, and (4) external audits. In line with this, during the interviews, before asking the metaphorical questions, the participants were asked to discuss what it meant for them being in a school context with a successful school principal (prolonged engagement). Further, literature examination was conducted before the analysis (triangulation). The detailed descriptions and analyses of the metaphorical data were ensured (rich, thick description). Further, the participants' own expressions have been included in the findings to ensure the trustworthiness, so several examples from the participants' expressions have been provided. Finally, the obtained data have been kept and are open to the external audits.

Findings

By conducting the interpretive content analysis, a variety of were revealed. During the analysis we sought for the traces of leadership attitudes and behaviors of successful school principals both in metaphors and their explanations. In this section, the elicited metaphors are interpreted in terms of their figurative meanings. Based on the findings are presented under two titles: (1) metaphors with interpretations and (2) leadership styles based on the metaphors and their explanations.

Metaphors on Successful School Principals

Following the analysis of the metaphors, there have been a total of 262 metaphors (84 by teachers, 18 by deputies, 89 by students, and 71 by parents) in this study. Table 2 presents the metaphors produced by the participants.

Table 2. Metaphors on Successful School Principals

Teachers' Metaphors							
	<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>
A father	30	A basketball coach	2	A sculptor	1	A surfer	1
A basketball player	24	A team player	2	Hulusi Kentmen	1	Water	1
My parent	12	A friend/companion	2	A law book	1	A super hero	1
A team captain	12	A fair king	1	A locomotive	1	Sugar	1
An orchestra conductor	10	An octopus	1	A flambeau	1	An umbrella	1
A bee	9	A respected elder	1	The captain of national team	1	A driver	1
A football coach	8	Şadırvan	1	An architect	1	The turtle beating the rabbit	1
A ship captain	8	A R&D manager	1	An engineer	1	Soil	1
A tree	7	A soldier	1	A labourer	1	Traffic lamps	1
A football player	7	A gardener	1	A school building	1	A pilot	1
A warrior on a horse	6	The backbone	1	A teacher	1	An experienced farmer	1
An ant	6	White clouds	1	A fountain	1	An easygoing person	1
A compass	4	A brain	1	A moderator	1	A space researcher	1
Light	4	A man on a knife-edge	1	A chef	1	A soldier for ages	1
Mevlâna	3	Infinite energy	1	An artist	1	A celebrity	1
Flower	3	A washing machine	1	A role model	1	A master chef	1
A scale	3	A mountaineer	1	A protagonist	1	Rain clouds	1
A leader	3	Rough sea	1	Wheels of a clock	1	A mother in the series	1
A child	2	A tomato	1	Salad dressing	1	Salt for food	1
The sun	2	Four season	1	A commander in the war	1	Yunus Emre	1
A north star	2	A ship	1	A politician	1	A desperate man	1
Deputies' Metaphors							
	<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>
A commander	2	A father	1	An air conditioner	1	A team leader	1
A big brother	1	Bozkurt	1	A harbour	1	A team player	1
Roots of a tree	1	Four seasons	1	Metehan	1	A pulled arrow string	1
A tree	1	An ideal principal	1	A tolerant person	1		
An octopus	1	An ant	1	The last warrior	1		
Students' Metaphors							
	<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>
A father	25	A flower	2	A dish washer	1	A commander	1
The sun	15	An optimist person	2	A CEO	1	A life saver	1
A tree	14	A candle	2	A president	1	A machine	1
A bee	10	A headmistress	2	A farmer	1	A monkey	1
An angle	9	A pomegranate	2	A cheetah	1	A mukhtar	1
A good person	9	A compass	2	A mountain	1	A food processor	1
A family	8	A scale	2	A man like a mountain	1	A navigator	1
Atatürk	5	A leader	2	Dede Korkut	1	A teacher	1
An ant	5	The roof of the school	2	A decisive person	1	A cotton	1
Light	5	A super hero	2	A tidy person	1	An aubergine	1
A benevolent person	4	A king	2	A littérateur	1	A police	1
A cotton candy	4	A qualified principal	2	A Sincere person	1	A respectful person	1

A gardener	4	A big brother	2	A best friend	1	A classmate	1
A book	4	A courthouse	1	A source of energy	1	A responsible person	1
A disciplinarian person	4	A pineapple	1	A ship wheel	1	An NGO	1
A friend	3	A mother	1	An interior designer	1	Water	1
A shield	3	My mothers' uncle	1	A human	1	Soil	1
A brain	2	A lion	1	A Swiss Army Pocket Knife	1	Sleep	1
My school principal	2	An almond	1	A captain	1	A life coach	1
A building foundation	2	An entrepreneur	1	A statesman with good character	1	A road	1
A washing machine	2	A hero	1	Light shining in the dark	1	A direction sign post	1
A plane tree	2	A designer	1	A guide	1	A manager	1

Parents' Metaphors

	<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>		<i>N</i>
A father	14	A business owner	1	A hero	1	A referee	1
A family	10	A cell	1	An honest person	1	A respected elder	1
A tree	10	A child	1	Hulusi Kentmen	1	A risk-taker	1
A bee	6	A clock	1	A judge	1	A rol model	1
The sun	6	A close relative	1	A knowledge treasure	1	A roof	1
A book	6	A commander	1	A navigator	1	A scale	1
An ant	5	A community leader	1	One of us	1	A school foundation	1
A leader	5	Cotton	1	One With Leadership Soul	1	A school leader	1
A friend	4	A disciplinarian instructor	1	A perfect leader	1	Shade of a tree	1
Light	3	An empathetic person	1	A perfect mother	1	A ship captain	1
A brain	2	A farmer	1	A poet	1	A sincere person	1
A mountain	2	Fatih Terim	1	A precious stone	1	A sturdy foundation	1
Mehmet Akif Ersoy	2	A flambeau	1	A president	1	A treasure	1
An angle	1	A forest	1	A prime minister	1	An understanding person	1
Atatürk	1	A funny person	1	A professional artist	1	A very successful person	1
An Athlete Running	1	A good person	1	A protector	1	A watchman	1
A big brother	1	A guide	1	A psychologist	1	Water	1
A bird	1	A hardworking person	1	A qualified researcher	1		

As shown in Table 2, teachers mostly consider their successful school principals as a father ($N = 30$), a basketball player ($N = 24$), my parent ($N = 12$), a team captain ($N = 12$), an orchestra conductor ($N = 10$), a bee ($N = 9$), a football coach ($N = 8$), a ship captain ($N = 8$), a tree ($N = 7$) and a football player ($N = 7$). Based on the findings, it can be suggested that teachers often see their principals as a caring, benevolent and moral identity. According to the most repeated metaphors, it can be noted successful school principals also lead the team and navigate the route based on the school goals. Deputies, on the other hand, often consider their successful school principals as a commander ($N = 2$), a big brother ($N = 1$), roots of a tree ($N = 1$), a tree ($N = 1$), an octopus ($N = 1$), a father ($N = 1$), Bozkurt (The Grizzly Wolf) ($N = 1$), four seasons ($N = 1$), an ideal principal ($N = 1$), an ant ($N = 1$), an air conditioner ($N = 1$), a harbour ($N = 1$), Metehan ($N = 1$), a tolerant person ($N = 1$), the last warrior ($N = 1$), a team leader ($N = 1$), and a pulled arrow

string ($N = 1$). Based on the findings, it can be suggested that deputies refer their principals as the authority. They also consider the school principals as strenuous members of the organization. When it comes to the students, they mostly consider their successful school principals as a father ($N = 25$), the sun ($N = 15$), a tree ($N = 14$), a bee ($N = 10$), an angle ($N = 9$), a good person ($N = 9$), a family ($N = 8$), Atatürk ($N = 5$), an ant ($N = 5$), and light ($N = 5$). Based on the findings, it can be suggested that students often see their principals as the affectionate person with authority. In other words, they trust their school principals just as they do in their family. Parents, on the other hand, mostly consider their successful school principals as a father ($N = 14$), a family ($N = 10$), a tree ($N = 10$), a bee ($N = 6$), the sun ($N = 6$), a book ($N = 6$), an ant ($N = 5$), a leader ($N = 5$), a friend ($N = 4$), and light ($N = 3$). Based on the findings, it can be suggested that parents and students mostly produced similar metaphors for their successful school principals. Students and parents are the service takers in school organizations and have expectations from the school principals. Therefore, this similarity can be attributed to this situation. To put it differently, the differences between teachers/deputies and students/parents may be caused from their roles in the school organizations.

When we examine the other metaphors, there are several unique metaphors which can be only produced or understood by those knowing the Turkish Culture. These metaphors are as follows: “*Mevlâna*”, “*Şadırvan*”, “*Hulusi Kentmen*”, “*the mother in the series called Yaprak Dökümü*”, broadcasted in 2016-2010, and “*Yunus Emre*” (Teachers), “*Bozkurt*” and “*Mevlana*” (Deputies), “*Atatürk*”, “*Dede Korkut*”, “*A Swiss Army Pocket Knife*”, and “*A muhktar*” (Students) and “*Mehmet Akif Ersoy*”, “*Atatürk*”, “*Fatih Terim*”, and “*Hulusi Kentmen*” (Parents). Based on an examination previous literature on metaphorical analysis on school principals, no research eliciting these metaphors on school principals has been found. Such metaphors as “*Atatürk*” and “*Hulusi Kentmen*” are included in a few studies: the former (Çobanoğlu & Gökalp, 2015; Yalçın & Erginer, 2012) and the latter (Dönmez, 2019; Görgülü, 2019). In this sense, it can be noted that almost these metaphors have emerged in this research. However, many others have been listed in a few studies in different contexts when compared to this research. Considering the research context in this study, the metaphors elicited on successful school principals are native to this study. Therefore, these metaphors can be seen an important contribution to the literature on school principalship, as well.

“*Atatürk*” is the founder of Turkish Republic and one the great commanders of Turkish History. Therefore, he has a very special meaning for Turkish people. The fact that the student and parent participants used this metaphor to depict their successful school principals can be said to hold important messages, which will be addressed in the discussion. Landau (1984) notes that Atatürk’s vision as a strategist and field commander in both the First World War and Türkiye’s War of Independence ensure his place among major world leaders, but he is most likely to be remembered as the builder and modernizer of the Turkish Republic (p. xi). Atatürk is a rare leaders who changed the course of history across the world (Ortaylı, 2018). The Atatürk metaphor is explained by the student and parent participants as follows:

My school principal is like Atatürk because she is a great leader like Atatürk. **S64**

My school principal is like Atatürk because he is ambitious and disciplined. There two traits are the ones of Atatürk, as well. **T121**

My school principal is like Atatürk because he has leadership skills that matter. **P83**

“*Mevlâna*”, called as Mowlana Jalaloddin Balkhi in Iran and Central Asia, RUMI in the west, or Mevlânâ Celâleddîn-i Rûmî in Türkiye, is a religious scholar interested in Sufism and mystic poetry, and lived in Konya, a city in the center of Anatolia although he was born in Balkh, a region between Afghanistan and Tajikistan (Mojaddedi, 2007). Mevlâna, living between 1207-1273, is famous for his *Masnavi*, a long and complex poem, written by Mevlâna. Mevlâna is considered as bridge between faiths in the history of religions (Bark, 2009, p.1). The “*Mevlâna*” metaphor is explained by the teacher participants as follows:

My school principal is like Mevlâna because he/she can welcome people from diverse background and does no discrimination. **T63**

My school principal is like Mevlâna because he/she never tends to allow discrimination or nepotism and loves humans just because they are humans. **T79**

My school principal is like Mevlâna because everybody can come up with new ideas and he/she supports all convenient ones. **T214**

“*Hulusi Kentmen*” was a famous Turkish actor who is known for such roles the boss or the father with his paternalist style in the Turkish Cinema. Aslan and Özer (2019) depicts him as a good person and trustworthy without doubt, and opine that he won the affection of people through such roles as boss or father in movies even though he sometimes treated his workers or children in his films since they know that he would display an authoritarian personality ex officio to protect them for the sake of their goodness and well-being. The “*Hulusi Kentmen*” metaphor is explained by the teacher and parent participants as follows:

My school principal is like Hulusi Kentmen because he treats us his children and protect us like a father. **T203**

My school principal is like Hulusi Kentmen because he is paternalist. **P129**

“*Dede Korkut*” is a well-known collection of stories set during the heroic age of the Oghuz Turks, but who compiled stories together is a matter of question inherited from the past (Lewis, 2011). The book of Dede Korkut is comprised of narratives of the traditional philosophy of Turks and their cultural roots (Köse, 2020). The “*Dede Korkut*” metaphor is explained by a student participant as follows:

My school principal is like Dede Korkut because he/she always gives advice, guides us towards what is useful for us, and treats us with affection like a father. **S92**

“*Fatih Terim*”, who was once the coach of the Turkish National Football team and the football club AC Milan in Italy, is the eminent football coach of Galatasaray football team in Türkiye. In his extensive research, McManus (2018) notes that some people considers him as exemplary, so he deserves a seat in the pantheon of the world’s greatest coaches, whereas others regard him as an egotistical tyrant. Blasing (2020), on the other hand, has a word in the book of McManus (2018), noting that some of the information in the book rests on news media and the author has written a book without knowing much in Turkish culture. In fact, this debate is the issue of in the football literature in Türkiye, but is important to make connection between the metaphor and Fatih Terim in our analysis. At this point, what we interest is in this research is his achievements. Galatasaray won the final match and became the first Turkish team to win a major European trophy in Copenhagen in 2000. This is a fact and above all the discussions about the style of Fatih Terim. According to Nuhrat (2019, p. 383), Fatih Terim is called as “*Emperor*” in Türkiye due to his glorious career. The “*Fatih Terim*” metaphor is explained by a parent participant as follows:

My school principal is like Fatih Terim because he/she puts his efforts to our success and motivates us to achieve. Further, he/she prepares the students behind for the next match and make them do trainings. **P71**

“*Mehmet Akif Ersoy*” was a significant Turkish poet, who lived between 1873-1936), and is an important figure in Turkish History in that he wrote the lyrics for the National Anthem of Türkiye. Upon the declaration of Turkish Republic on 23rd April 1920, it was decided to hold a contest among poets to write lyrics for the possible national anthem and defined an amount of money for prize, but no application was found to be worthy. Then, Mehmet Akif Ersoy was asked to write the lyrics, and he accepted this offer and didn't accept the prize due to his patriotism and ethical considerations, and donated to a charity (Önder, 1986). Another aspect of Mehmet Akif Ersoy was that he would focus on the problems of the society in this writing to raise an awareness in the society (Baş, 2012). The “Mehmet Akif Ersoy” metaphor is explained by parent participants as follows:

My school principal is like Mehmet Akif Ersoy because he/she loves his homeland very much and can sacrifice himself and do everything for his country. **P62**

My school principal is like Mehmet Akif Ersoy because he/she is very successful but doesn't like talking about his achievements. **P106**

“*Yunus Emre*” is a poet and is also another important figure in Turkish territories, who lived between at the second half of the 13th century and at the beginning of the 14th century despite the limited information about his life. According to Taştan (2019), Yunus Emre pioneered the development of Turkish mysticism thinking across the Anatolia, and was credited with the notions of peace and self-perception of humans. The “Yunus Emre” metaphor is explained by a teacher participant as follows:

My school principal is like Yunus Emre because he/she is very tolerant person. **T76**

“*Mete Han*” is the leader of the Great Hun Empire who reigned between 209 B.C. and 174 B.C in the Asia continent. He is known for the controlling a vast area in the Asia. He is known as Mao-tun in the records of Chinese remnants (Cengiz, 2017). Son of the Teoman (Tuman), who was the founder of Hun Empire, Mete Han, who had a difficult and feisty temperament, got all Turks together and went beyond the Great Wall of China, which had been claimed to be impassable (Sarı, 2016). The “Mete Han” metaphor is explained by a deputy participant as follows:

My school principal is like Mete Han because he leads the school like the commander Mete Han who led his army with his flag in his hand on the Tian Shan Mountains. **D13**

Considered as a companion that one can count on, “*the Swiss Army Pocketknife*” is a kind of multifunctional pocketknife produced by Victorinox. Those who may need to be ready for anything often use this knife as it is a trusted tool of adventurers (www.swissarmy.com). It is noted for its convenience for travellers (Özcan, 2019). The “the Swiss Army Pocketknife” metaphor is explained by a student participant as follows:

My school principal is like a Swiss Army Pocket Knife because he can do everything in the school. **S203**

“*Bozkurt*” is the Wolf which is said to have showed the exit to the Turks getting stuck in Ergenekon region, surrounded by the mountains according to Ergenekon Epic (Sarı İbrahim, 2016, 2017). The “Bozkurt” metaphor is explained by a deputy participant as follows:

My school principal is like Bozkurt in Ergenekon epic because he always navigates staff and students in the event of obstacles and during the hard times just as the bozkurt showed the way out Turks stucked in Ergenekon. **D12**

“*The Mukhtar*” is the name of the official representative of the state in the villages (www.icisleri.gov.tr). The concept of “mukhtar” emerged as a part of local administrarions during the Ottoman Empire period almost two centuries ago (Demir, 2019). It can be noted that mukhtars in the villages are considered the authority and people whose ideas are important. Further, it is sometimes a traditional position in most villages in Türkiye, which is handed down to the next generations. The “Mukhtar” metaphor is explained by a student participant as follows:

My school principal is like a Mukhtar because a mukhtar has the responsibility of a region and is a disciplined, patient, and self-esteemed person. Our school principal resembles a mukhtar who organizes everything. **S84**

“*The mother in the series Yaprak Dökümü*” is another metaphor native to this research. Indeed, this metaphor can be also interpreted as the sole negative metaphor elicited on successful school principalship. “*Yaprak Dökümü*” was a soup opera broadcasted in 2016-2010 in Türkiye, which was adapted by the novel of Reşat Nuri Güntekin, who was a famous writer in Turkish Literature. The “*The mother in the series Yaprak Dökümü*” metaphor is explained by a teacher participant as follows:

My school principal is like “*The mother in the series Yaprak Dökümü*” because he always ignores the adverse events or attempts to avoid conflicts. He tries to protect the positive school climate, delaying or articulating the problems. **T30**

The findings show that the participants in our study also produced similar metaphors in the literature, but there are still differences among the common metaphors between the past research findings and ours. Accordingly, the participants added some adjectives or words to reinforce the the metaphors to strenghten the meaning. This can be attributed to their efforts to make the meaning strong. For example, the participants used “*a warrior on a horse*” rather than “*a warrior*”, “*a super hero*” rather than “*hero*”, “*a plane tree*” rather than “*tree*”, “*the captain of national team*” rather than “*a team captain*”, “*a close relative*” rather than “*relative*”, “*a commander in the war*” rather than “*a commander*”, “*a community leader*” rather than “*a leader*”, “*knowledge treasure*” rather than “*treasure*”, “*a light shining in the dark*” rather than “*a light*”, “*a professional artist*” rather than “*artist*”, “*a space researcher*” rather than “*a researcher*”, and “*rain clouds*” or “*white clouds*” rather than “*clouds*”. This nature of some of the metaphor in our study can be said to have stemmed from the achievement culture in these schools. The successful school leadership characteristics, attitudes and behaviours must have affected the thinking’s of the participants. In this sense, while producing metaphors, they must have thought that the words may not have sufficiently represent their point of view towards the successful school leadership. This can be observed in the participants’ own expressions listed below:

socioeconomically disadvantage. In this sense, Crow, Day and Møller (2017) suggest that along with the professional, socially located dimensions of school principals' identity, the personal dimension includes such roles as father, son or partners according to the feedback from family (p. 270). Steyn (2014) conducted a study in a context in which successful school leadership with people oriented were observed, and concluded based on the teachers' data that the school principal was regarded as a "real father figure", protecting and respecting staff as well as giving them space to do things. Several examples from the participants' expressions on the "*father*" metaphor are included below:

My school principal is like a father because he administers this school, which is a very big family with the affection of a father as well as his authority and keep us together. **T24**

My school principal is like the leader of our family because he is open-minded, and we can consult and ask for help and support for everything. He has also good sense of humour. **D10**

My school principal is like a father because he attaches great importance to our education. Just as it is the same for a father, the wishes of the students are important for him. **S87**

My school principal is like a father because he always treats our children as if they were his own children. He always wishes the success and wellness for the students as it is in his own family. To achieve this, he always asks for feedback about the students. **P8**

Another common metaphor is "*the commander*". This metaphor shows that the participants consider their school principals as the authority. This can also be attributed to paternalist context due to the authoritarian dimension of the paternalistic leadership (Farh and Cheng, 2000). Several examples from the participants' expressions on the "*the commander*" metaphor is included below:

My school principal is like a commander, even a warrior on a horse because he always sheds lights on through his expertise and leadership skills. **T95**

My school principal is like a commander because he treats us well and leads, by motivating the challenges. **D8**

My school principal is like a commander because he expects strict discipline from us. **S150**

My school principal is like a commander because he exerts discipline over students and teachers in a respectful manner and administers the school. **P91**

The "ant" is also uttered by all participants. Bruce-Mitford, M. (2008) conceptualizes the meaning of the word "ant" as "it reflects industrious, orderly behavior, and signifies fertility (P.73). Further, it is noted by Ferber (2007) that the ant is credited with its wisdom, prudence, and foresight. The ant is known for its wisdom, prudence, or foresight. The reason why all participants produced ant can be attributed to the reputations of the successful school principals in the research context. Several examples from the participants' expressions on the "ant" metaphor are included below:

My school principal is like a leader ant because he is both a leader and a hardworking person. He gives great efforts when doing a task. He is decisive and self-sacrifice. He always creates new paths for teachers and students. **T130**

My school principal is like an ant because he never stops working. **S4**

The last common metaphor is "*the tree*". Goddard (2001) highlights that such concepts as bird, fish and tree are far from universal and these words may have different meanings in different languages. Regarding the meaning of tree in terms of metaphors, Ferber (2007) note that "anything

that can grow, “flourish,” bear “fruit,” and die might be likened to a tree: a person, a family, a nation, a cultural tradition (p. 219). In this research, as far as it is understood by the explanations of the metaphors, the participants used this metaphor to emphasize the productive sides of their successful school principals. Several examples from the participants’ expressions on the “the tree” metaphor are included below:

My school principal is like the roots of a tree because the other staff are the branches and the leaves. If the roots are powerful, the rest will be strong, too. **T9**

My school principal is like the roots of a tree because he grows students on his branches and leads them to be successful through the system he sets. He makes teachers happy. **D11**

My school principal is like a tree because a tree gives fruits to people just as my principal gives information to us. **S128**

Other common metaphors are presented in groups with three and two similar metaphors as codes (TSP, DSP, TP, TS, SP, TD). In this sense, bee, brain, friend, leader, light, scales, sun, water, farmer are included in group TSP, while big brother is the metaphor shared by DSP. Angle, Atatürk, book, cotton, disciplinarian, family, good person, guide, hero, mountain, navigator, president, and roof are the metaphors by SP. Child, flambeau, Hulusi Kentmen, Respected elder in the family, role model, and ship captain are the ones by TP. Compass, flower, gardener, soil, super hero, teacher, and washing machine are the ones by TS. Four seasons, octopus, and team player are the metaphors included in the group TD. In this sense, 43 metaphors are common by different group of participants in the groups with four, three and two participant categories.

Leadership Styles by Successful School Principals

School leadership theory is a trend issue among researchers, and the theories existing gain popularity over time or vice versa. most of the time, what leads to such changes cannot be exactly revealed (Bush & Glover, 2014). during this part of the analysis, we relied on both the and explanations. on the other hand, Bush and Glover (2014) opine that school leadership models have artificial distinctions since in most successful school leaders may employ most or all of these approaches. In this sense, this is also available in this paper, but we attempted to assign the metaphors based on the most apparent characteristics of leadership types, and it can be thought that this can provide an insight the most employed or desired school leadership types in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts. we relied on explanations more than the metaphors themselves for this analysis. therefore, a similar metaphor has been assigned more than one leadership type.

Based on the analysis, the metaphors are classified into the school leadership styles as follows: Paternalistic School Leadership ($N = 175$), Transformational School Leadership ($N = 107$), Charismatic School Leadership ($N = 81$), Distributed/Teacher School Leadership ($N = 74$), Ethical/Moral/Values School Leadership ($N = 63$), Servant School Leadership ($N = 45$), Social Justice/Culturally Responsive School Leadership ($N = 33$) and Instructional School Leadership ($N = 25$).

The analysis of metaphors and their explanations show that teachers, deputies, students and parents mostly care about the positive school climate and school culture in their socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts. What is interesting is that instructional school leadership has the lowest frequency when compared to others. On the other hand, considering the selection criteria of the

schools, the school principals and the participants in this study after a rigid process based on several criteria's, this can be regarded as a paradox. However, school principalship is not a sole profession in Türkiye but a temporary one that is assigned to teachers following several steps, including exams and interviews. Therefore, the best teachers with exemplary instructional skills aren't always assigned as school principals in Türkiye. Instead, successful school principals mostly can improve schools and increase achievement through teachers and their characteristic natures. This motivates teachers, deputies, students and parents to be successful. Bush and Glover (2014) well explains school leadership models are partial and provide distinct but uni-dimensional perspectives and artificial distinctions, or 'ideal types', in that most successful leaders are likely to embody most or all of these approaches (p. 565).

Several metaphors like father, the sun, tree, bee, ant, family have been included in more than one school leadership style. This is because there are no sharp distinctions among school leaderships styles as also noted by Bush and Glover (2014). The Successful School Leadership Model based on the metaphors in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Successful school leadership with metaphors in socioeconomically school context

Metaphors related to Paternalist School Leadership

The metaphors related to paternalistic school leadership are as follows: “a father” (N = 55); “a family” (N = 15), “a bee” (N = 8), “a strong plane tree” (N = 5), “a disciplined person” (N = 5), “a good manager” (N = 4), “a mother” (N = 4); “a mountain” (N = 4); “a roof” (N = 3); “a commander” (N = 3); “a tree” (N = 4); “a friend” (N = 3); “a respected elder in the family” (N = 3), “a good person” (N = 3); “a benevolent person” (N = 3); “a good person” (N = 3); “the trunk of a tree” (N = 2); “a shield” (N = 2); “the roots of a tree” (N = 2); “an elder brother” (N = 2); “a king” (N = 2); “the foundation of the building” (N = 2) and “Hulusi Kentmen” (N = 2). Further, there are other metaphors included in paternalistic school leadership style as follows: “an aubergine” (S165), “a bird” (P30), “a classmate” (S140), “a clock” (P1), “cotton” (S29), “a flower” (S86), “a funny person” (S79), “a gardener” (S133), “a harbor” (D14), “a hero” (S147), “a kind person” (P117), “a lion” (S212), “a master chef” (T178), “a monkey” (S145), “a mukhtar” (S84), “one of us” (P44), “an orchestra conductor” (T118), “a police” (S8), “a protector” (P111), “a referee” (P108), “rough sea” (T96), “a scale” (T98), “a sister” (T46), “a smiling person” (S49), “solar system” (S219), “a sympathetic person” (P128), “a teacher” (S76), “a tolerant person” (S191), “traffic lambs” (T35), “an umbrella” (T172) and “a watchman” (P55). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in paternalistic school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like a mother or a sister because we can share our problems without time restrictions. We can share our joys and sorrows, as well. She pushes her limits to help us. Like a woman warrior, she stands up to the challenges for our wellness. **T43**

My school principal is like a safe harbour because he bravely and generously hosts and helps us whenever we have problems. **D14**

My school principal is like a father because he protects us against every kind of threat, tries to help us, and shows affection towards us. **S11**

My school principal is like a mother who cares her children, focus her efforts on children’s well-being, and share their feelings, such as happiness or sadness because she treats our children as if they were her children. **P34**

The metaphor in this category shows that paternalist leadership style is the most favored one in Turkish context, particularly in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts. It is worth noting that successful school principals embrace many different school leadership styles in schools in their daily routines (Mungal & Sorenson, 2020). On the other hand, one explanation as to why paternalist school leadership was coded more than others could be the cultural elements of Turkish culture, based on the collectivist nature. The findings show that teachers provide effective instruction and students learn better when there is a family like school culture in which people respect, support and develop each other. Such metaphors as a father, a family, a strong plane tree, a disciplinarian person, a mother, a mountain, a commander, a benevolent person, Hulusi Kentmen and an umbrella are included in the paternalistic school leadership style.

Metaphors related to Transformational School Leadership

The metaphors related to transformational school leadership are as follows: “a tree” (N = 10), “a bee” (N = 8), “an ant” (N = 7), “a book” (N = 5), “light” (N = 6), “a compass” (N = 4), “a gardener” (N = 4), “a basketball player” (N = 3), “a brain” (N = 3), “source of energy” (N = 3), “the sun” (N = 3), “a farmer” (N = 3), “a team captain” (N = 3), “a leader” (N = 2), “soil” (N = 2), “an octopus” (N = 2), “a washing machine” (N = 2) and “a captain” (N = 2). Further, there are

other metaphors included in transformational school leadership style as follows: “*an architect*” (T196), “*an artist*” (P121), “*the captain of national team*” (T10), “*a cell*” (P27), “*a CEO*” (S55), “*a designer*” (S194), “*a direction sign post*” (S95), “*a dish washer*” (S30), “*an engineer*” (T166), “*an entrepreneur*” (S19), “*a father*” (P113), “*a food processor*” (S216), “*a friend*” (P51), “*a guide*” (P14), “*a hardworking person*” (P40), “*an interior designer*” (S60), “*knowledge treasure*” (P93), “*a locomotive*” (T231), “*a machine*” (S175), “*a manager*” (S176), “*a navigation*” (P107), “*a parent*” (P25), “*a pulled arrow string*” (D5), “*a researcher*” (P86), “*a role model*” (T84), “*a saver*” (S200), “*the school building*” (T182), “*a sculptor*” (T39), “*a statesman with good character*” (S5), “*a successful person*” (P42), “*the roots of a tree*” (T133), “*a tomato*” (T48), “*treasure*” (P52) and “*the turtle beating the rabbit*” (T230). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in transformational school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like a team captain because he always motivates us. Although there were many disadvantages in our school when he arrived, he put great efforts and changed the nature of our school culture. Further, he made everyone believe in him. **T20**

My school principal is like an octopus because he always engages in multitask works. He is always busy with every issue in the school and supports everyone in the school. **D3**

My school principal is like a life saver because he has changed our school from a ruin to a palace. Our school is a very nice place now. **S200**

My school principal is like a farmer because he works during the years so that the fruits and vegetables in his garden can take the water and sunlight needed for their survivals. He becomes happy when the fruits and vegetables grow and become delicious as he wishes. **P72**

The metaphors in this category shows that transformational school leadership style is the second one with more frequency rate. The participants drew attention to the transformational process both in the physical conditions and academic achievement in their schools. The successful school principals must have relied on some interventions to make a difference in their schools. This may have impacted the metaphorical perceptions of the participants. Such metaphors as a tree, a bee, an ant, a compass, a gardener, the sun, an architect, an artist, a designer, and a locomotive are included in the transformational school leadership style.

Metaphors related to Charismatic School Leadership

The metaphors related to charismatic school leadership are as follows: “the sun” (N = 7), “Atatürk” (N = 6), “a school leader” (N = 3), “a basketball player” (N = 3), “a compass” (N = 3), “a team captain” (N = 3), “a father” (N = 3), “the president” (N = 3), “Mehmet Akif Ersoy” (N = 2), “a tree” (N = 2), “a child” (N = 2), “light” (N = 2), “a ship captain” (N = 2), “a football captain” (N = 2) and “the north star” (N = 2). Further, there are other metaphors included in charismatic school leadership style as follows: “an air conditioner” (D2), “a bee” (T199), “a book” (S132), “a candle” (S16), “a captain” (P69), “Dede Korkut” (S92), “a driver” (T202), “an experienced soldier” (T38), “a family leader” (T97), “Fatih Terim” (P71), “a flambeau” (P54), “a flower” (T139), “four season” (D18), “a friend” (T103), “a good leader” (T73), “a good manager” (S54), “a hero” (P48), “a leader” (P50), “a littérateur” (S2), “a man on a knife-edge” (T128), “my school principal” (S10), “a pilot” (T229), “a poet” (P2), “a precious stone” (P23), “a prime minister” (P102), “a respected person” (S26), “a road” (S213), “sleep” (S107), “a snowdrop flower” (T47), “a space researcher” (T28), “a super hero” (S105), “Superman” (S206), “a surfer”

(T222), “a warrior on a horse” (T5) and “wheels of a clock” (T18). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in charismatic school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like a team captain because he makes us feel happy and relax as soon as we enter the school. His sincere approach makes us feel that the school is our home rather than a workplace. As a result, we, as a team with high motivations, can do useful works. **T132**

My school principal is like the four seasons because he is ready for all kind of situations, positive or negative. **D18**

My school principal is like the Atatürk because he has a decisive personality and a real leader. **S124**

My school principal is like a prime minister because he does his best for our children like a statesman who wants the best for the country. **P102**

The metaphor in this category shows that charismatic school leadership style is also popular in the successful schools in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts. The findings clearly show that the participants consider their successful school principals as very important historical figures in Turkish culture. Such metaphors as Atatürk, Mehmet Akif Ersoy, the north star, Dede Korkut, Fatih Terim, a hero, a littérateur, a space researcher, a superman, and a warrior on a horse are included in the charismatic school leadership style.

Metaphors related to Distributed/Teacher School Leadership

The metaphors related to distribute/teacher school leadership are as follows: “*a basketball player*” ($N = 23$), “*an orchestra conductor*” ($N = 11$), “*a team leader*” ($N = 11$), “*a team player*” ($N = 5$), “*a football coach*” ($N = 4$), “*a leader*” ($N = 4$), “*a father*” ($N = 3$) and “*an ant*” ($N = 2$). Further, there are other metaphors included in distribute/teacher school leadership style as follows: “*an artist*” (T87), “*a basketball coach*” (T51), “*a big brother*” (D9), “*a commander*” (T126), “*a flower*” (*rose*) (T15), “*a friend/companion*” (T72), “*a moderator*” (T3), “*R&D manager*” (T78), “*roots of a tree*” (D11), “*a ship captain*” (T68), “*the sun*” (T64). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in distribute/teacher school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like a football coach because he determines the strategy and tactics for the team and the team leads to success. **T16**

My school principal is like the roots of a tree because he grows lots of successful students on his branches. Further, the teachers working with him are happy individuals who have nice workplaces. **D9**

The metaphor in this category shows that distributed/teacher school leadership style is also among the findings in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts. The metaphors and their explanations reveal that successful school principals are aware of the fact that victory is not a sole destination. They collaborate with others and lead to their schools to the peaks of the achievement. Such metaphors as a basketball player, an orchestra conductor, a team player, a team leader, a football coach, a leader, a father, a basketball coach, a commander, and a moderator are included in the distributed/teacher school leadership style.

Metaphors related to Ethical/Moral School Leadership

The metaphors related to ethical/moral school leadership are as follows: “*an angle*” ($N = 8$), “*a father*” ($N = 6$), “*a good person*” ($N = 6$), “*the sun*” ($N = 4$), “*a cotton candy*” ($N = 4$), “*a sincere person*” ($N = 2$), “*water*” ($N = 2$), “*a pomagranate*” ($N = 2$) and “*scale*” ($N = 2$). Further, there are other metaphors included in ethical/moral school leadership style as follows: “*an ant*” (T220), “*the backbone*” (T92), “*a best friend*” (S109), “*a captain*” (T74), “*a commander*” (D8), “*a community leader*” (P70), “*cotton*” (P26), “*a decisive person*” (S18), “*an easygoing person*” (T157), “*a forest*” (P37), “*the foundation of a school*” (P96), “*a friend*” (P100), “*a hardworking person*” (P81), “*a human*” (S20), “*a law book*” (T160), “*Mevlana*” (T79), “*an NGO*” (S96), “*a politician*” (T212) “*psychologist*” (P79), “*role model teacher*” (P75), “*salt of the food*” (T124), “*a shield*” (S110), “*a ship captain*” (T142), “*a tidy person*” (S154), “*an understanding person*” (P132), “*a washing machine*” (T2) and “*white clouds*” (T169). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in ethical/moral school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like a commander who treats teachers, students and parents well and shows empathy, by motivating them. **D8**

My school principal is like Mevlâna because our school principal’s philosophy can be seen in the famous saying of Mevlana: “*Come, come, whoever you are.*” He never discriminates others. **T79**

My school principal is like an NGO because he always helps people, shares their problems. He forgives and helps even if we make mistakes. **S96**

My school principal is like a comrade because he always treats us like his friends or companions with whom he can collaborate while dealing with the issues on our children. **P100**

The metaphor in this category shows that ethical/moral school leadership style emerged from the findings. This provides evidence that successful school principal displays ethical behaviours and are committed to moral values in Turkish Culture. The participants’ metaphors and explanations point to the fact that people attach great importance to being ethical, moral, trustable and sincere. Such metaphors as an angle, a father, the sun, a cotton candy, a sincere person, water, a community leader, a law book, Mevlana and white clouds are included in the ethical/moral school leadership style.

Metaphors related to Servant School Leadership

The metaphors related to servant school leadership are as follows: “*a bee*” ($N = 9$), “*an ant*” ($N = 9$), “*a father*” ($N = 3$), “*a candle*” ($N = 2$) and “*a warrior on a horse*”. Further, there are other metaphors included in servant school leadership style as follows: “*a bird*” (P9), “*a mother*” (T180), “*a plane tree*” (P10), “*water*” (P19), “*an angle*” (P112), “*a sportman*” (P120), “*a lion*” (T146), “*a responsible person*” (S142), “*a swimmer*” (T147), “*the foundation of a building*” (S193), “*a Swiss army pocket knife*” (S203), “*a captain*” (T99), “*a cheetah*” (S215), “*a good manager*” (D16), “*a tolerant person*” (D17), “*a fountain*” (T13), “*a tree*” (T23), “*a woman warrior*” (T50), “*an elder brother*” (T61) and “*the sun*” (T94). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in servant school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like a traditional warrior called as Amazon Warrior because she is a successful school principal as a female administrator. The Amazon women led the tribes in old times. Similarly, she manages and administers our school. **T50**

My school principal is like a candle because he spends his energy for us and melts himself. He is a very self-sacrificing person. **S192**

The metaphor in this category shows that servant school leadership style emerged from the findings. It is seen that for being a successful school leader who leads to student achievement and school improvement requires great effort. Such metaphors as a bee, an ant, a father, a candle, a warrior on a horse, a bird, the foundation of a building, a Swiss Army Pocketknife, a fountain and Şadırvan are included in the servant school leadership style.

Metaphors related to Social Justice/Culturally Responsive School Leadership

The metaphors related to social justice/culturally responsive school leadership are as follows: “*the sun*” ($N = 4$), “*a father*” ($N = 3$), “*a family*” ($N = 3$), “*a scale*” ($N = 2$) and “*an angle*” ($N = 2$). Further, there are other metaphors included in social justice/culturally responsive school leadership style as follows: “*an almond*” (S161), “*a bee*” (P119), “*a book*” (S14), “*a close relative*” (P73), “*a courthouse*” (S220), “*a friend*” (P15), “*a judge*” (P16), “*a lamp*” (S37), “*a leader*” (P36), “*a life coach*” (S43), “*light*” (S58), “*Mevlana*” (T63), “*my characteristics*” (S207), “*a pineapple*” (S158) “*a protagonist*” (T98), “*a scale*” (T154), “*a ship wheel*” (S164), “*a sibling*” (P82) and “*a tree*” (S170). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in social justice/culturally responsive school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like Mevlana because he respects all kinds of opinions. **T63**

My school principal is like the sun because he saves us from the darkness of the life and provides opportunities. **S36**

My school principal is like a judge because he cares about the justice among the school, particularly for students. **P16**

The metaphor in this category shows that social justice/culturally responsive leadership style emerged from the findings, as well. This leadership style reflects the successful school principals’ understanding the context in their schools. In other words, they know the needs of the stakeholders and determine the pathways of the success. Such metaphors as the sun, a father, a family, a scale, an angle, a close relative, a courthouse, a judge, Mevlana and a protagonist are included in the social justice/culturally school leadership style.

Metaphors related to Instructional School Leadership

The metaphors related to instructional school leadership are as follows: “*the sun*” ($N = 5$), “*a book*” ($N = 4$), “*a tree*” ($N = 4$), “*light*” ($N = 2$), “*a leader*” ($N = 2$) and “*a brain*” ($N = 2$). Further, there are other metaphors included in instructional school leadership style as follows: “*a flambeau*” (T95), “*a flower*” (S12), “*a navigation*” (S173), “*rain clouds*” (T14), “*a teacher*” (T186) and “*team coach*” (T193). Some of the explanations of the metaphors in instructional school leadership style are as follows:

My school principal is like a flambeau because he always navigates us through his experiences. **T95**

My school principal is like a leader because he leads students to what is good. **S112**

My school principal is like a tree because the students are the fruit-buds of this tree and it cares about them. Finally, the tree bears delicious and ripe fruits. **P49**

The metaphor in this category shows that instructional school leadership style is also a leadership style adopted by successful school leaders. On the other hand, the fact that this is the least leadership style which was coded in the analyses is a surprising one, indeed. The reason why this paradox is that we recruited a diverse participant from successful schools with successful school principals whose academic achievements had been confirmed. The literature shows that instructional school leadership is directly related to student achievement (Reitzug, West & Angel, 2008) as it can be understood from the name of this school leadership style literally. However, this is the least mentioned in the metaphorical perceptions of the participants. This finding may be attributed to the fact that the participants may consider the teaching is the role of teachers, so may the achievements. The school principals may be considered as the one who prepare necessary conditions for teachers and students, namely positive school climate. Further, school principalship is not a sole profession in educational administration in Türkiye, and the school principalship is a temporary position for teachers. Therefore, school principals aren't provided special school principal preparation programmes or school leadership programmes as it is in the West. This means the successful school principals could win the victory by creating positive school culture and lead to the better student achievements and school improvements. Then, the stakeholders can accomplish their own responsibilities better. Such metaphors as the sun, a book, a tree, light, a brain, a flambeau, a flower, a navigator, rain clouds and a teacher are included in the social justice/culturally school leadership style.

Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

This qualitative inquiry was an attempt to determine the favoured school leadership styles in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts in Turkish Education System through metaphorical perceptions of teachers, deputies, students, and parents. Previous literature has revealed a plethora of studies on metaphorical perceptions on school principals in general. With a few studies on successful school leadership based on the metaphors (Parylo & Zepeda, 2014; Trnavčević, & Roncelli Vaupot, 2009), this study has yielded fruitful outcomes in terms of both metaphors and successful school leadership.

In our analysis, we found that a commander, a tree, a father and an ant are the common metaphors by all participants, followed by gardener, washing machine, compass, soil, flower and superhero. Further, a father, a tree, a bee, a basketball a player, the sun, a family, an ant, light, a team captain, and an orchestra conductor are the ones with the highest frequency. An examination of literature has shown that these are the common metaphors on school principals in Turkish Context, as well (Akan, Yalçın, & Yıldırım, 2014; Akın-Kösterelioğlu, 2014; Akyol & Kapçak, 2017; Çobanoğlu & Gökalp, 2015; Koçak, 2011; Korkmaz & Çevik, 2018; Özgenel & Gökçe, 2019; Pesen, Kara & Gedik, 2015; Yalçın & Erginer, 2012; Zembat, Tunçeli & Akşin, 2015). The reason why the participants mostly refer their school principals as a father can be attributed to the paternalist nature of Turkish Context (Aycan, 2001; Aycan, Kanungo, & Mendonça, 2016; Dağlı, & Ağalday, 2017). This is explained by Zembat, Tunçeli and Akşin (2015) as people in Türkiye consider their school principals as integrative and knowledgeable individuals who navigates them. Akan, Yalçın and Yıldırım (2014), on the other hand, attribute this to the administrative styles and the bureaucratic nature of school principals as much as the education system. Further, Özgenel and

Gökçe (2019) conclude that students consider their schools as their own home and the second family after their own one, so the school principal is the father of this second home.

In this study, no negative metaphors have been revealed. This may have been the recruitment process and the nature of this research that delves into the successful school principalship. However, past research has provided mostly negative metaphors on school principals along with the positive ones (Örücü, 2014; Pesen, Kara & Gedik, 2015). This is found as a though-provoking findings by Örücü (2014), emphasizing that the school principals who were once teachers themselves may have changed due to systematic and individual causes, so this may account for the negative perceptions. Pesen, Kara and Gedik (2015), on the other hand, draw to the attention to the fact that the negative perceptions on school principals may have stemmed from that the pre-service teachers weren't accepted as real teachers by the school principals in their internship periods and treated accordingly, so they had negative images on school principals.

This study, on the other hand, has contributed to the literature on metaphorical analysis on school principals in two ways: providing new metaphors and delving into the metaphorical analysis successful school principalship rather than just school principalship. In this sense, when we interpret the metaphors by all participants along with the other common sets in the Figure 1 (TP, TS, SP, TD, TSP, DSP), it can be suggested that the metaphors corroborated with the previous literature. In this sense, Parylo and Zepeda (2014) conducted membership categorization analysis on effective school principals based on the perceptions of the central office leaders and concluded that an instructional leader, a team player, a perfect fit, a data leader, a community leader, a good manager, and a passionate leader are the representations of the effective school principals. The authors found that effective school principal is a devoted and caring leader and has the passion for kids and love for education. They also revealed that effective school principal is a team player, a good communicator, and a community leader.

In our analysis, the metaphors such as “Mevlana”, “Şadırvan”, “Hulusi Kentmen”, “the mother in the series called *Yaprak Dökümü*”, broadcasted in 2016-2010, and “Yunus Emre” (Teachers), “Bozkurt” and “Mevlana” (Deputies), “Atatürk”, “Dede Korkut”, “A Swiss Army Pocket Knife”, and “A muhtar” (Students) and “Mehmet Akif Ersoy”, “Atatürk”, “Fatih Terim”, and “Hulusi Kentmen” are the new, salient metaphors, and they can be said to represent the devoted and caring qualities of successful school principals.

These figures have important places in Turkish Culture. In this sense, Hulusi Kentmen, for example, is considered by Karaçizmeli and Kesken (2017) as an authoritarian and benevolent administrator image, highlighted by Likert (1967). In this image, Hulusi Kentmen was a paternalist but sometimes angry person who had a deep impact on Turkish people in the Turkish movies (Aslan & Özer, 2019).

When we consider the leadership styles emerging in our analysis, there is evidence to support in the literature. For example, Dağlı and Ağalday (2017) noted that paternalist school leadership was found to be the highest score in the moral and benevolent subdimensions, concluding that school principals care about stakeholders, particularly protecting the teachers from external criticisms or threats. Further, several studies have found negative correlations between paternalistic school leadership styles and negative issues, such as political tactics (Aktaş, 2019). From this point, it can be concluded that paternalistic school leadership really matters in such collectivist contexts as it is in Türkiye. There are also several studies lending support to this conclusion in Turkish contexts (Ağalday, & Dağlı, 2019; Aycan, 2001; Bolat, Seymen, Bolat,

Kinter, & Katı, 2018; Dağlı & Ağalday, 2018; Dursun, 2019; Erben, & Güneşer, 2008; Tan, & Dimmock, 2014; Uğurluoğlu, Aldoğan, Turgut, & Özatkan, 2018).

Bouchamma (2012) found in the study conducted in disadvantaged areas of Canada that effective school leadership practices are establishing goals and expectations; strategic resourcing; curriculum management; teacher supervision and coaching; ensuring order and support. The author focused their findings on instructional leadership style. Despite the least leadership style in terms of frequency, instructional leadership is among the findings in this study. Robinson, Lloyd and Rowe (2008) conducted a meta-analysis research and concluded that the average effect of instructional leadership on student outcomes was three to four times that of transformational leadership. In a study by Day & Gu (2018), it was noted that successful school principals in disadvantaged contexts have strong moral values and purposes, firmly aiming at providing the students with the best learning opportunities, and this underpins a strong sense of collective commitment to change by staff.

Successful school principals in disadvantaged contexts don't engage in school leadership that accepts the status quo. Instead, they follow the change which is triggered by a passionate belief in inclusivity and trust, core values and is pursued by transformational leadership focusing on improvement of achievement within ethics of care, compassion, and social justice (Day, 2005). In this study, according to the metaphors and explanations, the successful school principals are considered as change agents who create positive school climate. In the extensive meta-analysis by Marzano, Waters and McNulty (2005), it was concluded that transformational, servant, situational and instructional school leadership matter in student achievement.

Successful school principals are the ones who never fear from risk-taking and continuously look for new opportunities and experiences for the students to achieve more. While doing this, they need to be resilient themselves (Day, 2014). In our findings, the charismatic, servant and social justice/culturally responsive school leadership styles can be evaluated in terms of their resilience. The metaphors such as Atatürk, Mehmet Akif Ersoy, Fatih Terim are the figures who struggled much and achieved in their lives for their countries. This perception of the participants can be attributed to this resilience which they may have observed in their school principals' attitudes and behaviours.

In the study conducted by Day, Gu, and Sammons (2016), it was concluded that school improvement and student achievement are not primarily the result of school principal leadership style but of their diagnosis of the schools and students' needs, so successful school principals don't necessarily have to be heroic in the traditional sense, but need to possess common values and traits, including clarity of vision, determination, responsiveness, courage of conviction, openness, fairness as well as clearly articulated moral and ethical values shared by their colleagues. However, they noted that not only transformational but also instructional school leadership are essential for success.

Based on the findings and discussions above, this research, delving into the metaphorical perceptions of teachers, deputies, students, and parents in terms of successful school principalship, has been an attempt to draw some conclusions the school leadership styles. Even though the primary concern is not to reveal a rank among the school leadership theories, paternalist, transformational, charismatic and distributed school leadership styles have been found to be the most favored ones when compared to ethical/moral/values, servant, social justice/culturally responsive instructional school leadership styles.

Focusing on successful school principalship from inside the schools with metaphors, this study can draw new theoretical implications. First, school principals should embrace paternalistic school leadership attitudes and behaviours if they are to increase student achievement and school improvement. Second, being ethical and moral is of great importance in a culture based on close relations. Therefore, effective communication and egalitarian attitudes can build trust in schools. Second, the school principalship must be a separate profession and the candidates can have professional training before leading a school. At least, in Türkiye, for some school principals, the school leadership may have been learned through trial-error methods, but the schools are not so vulnerable that one can test several strategies. Instead, professional with expertise on school management, administration and leadership must lead schools.

When it comes to the practical implications of this study, it can be noted that in order for being a successful school principal in Turkish contexts, current school principals or those dreaming to be one in the future must figure out that close relations, being fair, standing strong, even sometimes being authoritarian but not autocrat matter in school leadership. Therefore, being able to hold the power like a father but being able to be affectionate like a mother can inspire people in schools. This paves the way for change and success. School principals must pay utmost care to every words of their expressions, every aspect of their attitudes and behaviours and every result of their decisions.

No research that is not objected to limitations can be found (Bloomberg & Volpe, 2008). This study is also subjected to several limitations. First, the research size selection poses two limitations: (1) context of successful schools and successful school principals and (2) the school level. There would have been different metaphors in different school levels, primary or high schools, even vocational high schools. Further, if we think that Türkiye is a country with diverse cultures, there may be different metaphors and leadership styles in different parts of the country. For the future research, it can be suggested that a study like this can be conducted in different regions. Second, this study is based on the metaphorical perceptions of the participants. New inquiries with different research methods and participants (e.g., successful school principals themselves) can provide new evidence in terms of successful school principalship. Further, a similar study can be conducted in different parts of the world, especially in the Western countries in which individualism is dominant so that new data can be obtained to make comparisons.

Implications

Theoretical Implications

This study enhances the current body of knowledge by highlighting the significance of culturally relevant leadership styles in educational environments, specifically in socioeconomically disadvantaged contexts in Türkiye. It enhances the comprehension of how metaphorical perspectives can influence the conceptualization of successful school leadership. The results emphasize the importance of paternalistic leadership in the educational setting in Türkiye. This is consistent with prior research on collectivist cultures, but it goes further by establishing a link between specific metaphors and paternalistic characteristics. This enhances the theoretical framework for understanding leadership styles in various cultural contexts. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of metaphorical analysis in revealing underlying perceptions of leadership attributes. This proposes an innovative method for conducting educational research, highlighting the significance of metaphorical language in uncovering intricate and subtle perspectives on leadership. This study examines various leadership metaphors and affirms the notion that different leadership styles (such as transformational, charismatic, and distributed) can

coexist and yield positive results, contingent upon cultural and contextual factors. The inclusion of ethical and moral values in leadership, as demonstrated using metaphors, enhances our comprehension of successful leadership in the field of education. It implies that ethical considerations are essential in how leadership is perceived and implemented.

Practical Implications

The findings of this study can be used to shape the structure of leadership development programs in Türkiye, with a focus on highlighting paternalistic, ethical, and moral aspects. For individuals who aspire to become school principals, it is especially important to receive specialized training that corresponds to these culturally specific leadership expectations. These insights can be utilized by educational policymakers to develop strategies and policies that align with cultural norms and encourage leadership styles. This may involve promoting specific leadership behaviours or reconsidering the procedures for recruiting and assessing school principals. To prioritize the significance of intimate connections and moral conduct, school principals ought to concentrate on cultivating proficient communication abilities and nurturing egalitarian relationships within educational institutions. This may result in heightened confidence and a more favourable atmosphere within the school. The study emphasizes the significance of adjusting leadership styles to the socio-cultural environment of a school. School principals should be aware of and understand the values and expectations of the local community and adjust their approach accordingly. The study's limitations point to areas for future research, including exploring metaphorical perceptions across different educational levels and regions in Türkiye, and contrasting these findings with contexts where individualistic values predominate. This has the potential to enhance our comprehension of how culture impacts leadership in the field of education. In summary, the study establishes a connection between theoretical concepts and practical applications in the field of educational leadership. It provides valuable perspectives for educators, policymakers, and researchers working in culturally diverse contexts.

Acknowledgements

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sector.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest related to the research, methodology, or findings presented in this paper. All collaborations between the authors were strictly for academic and research purposes, and no financial or other personal interests influenced the outcome of this work.

Ethics

The ethical issues were our main priority. First, the official permission from the Ministry of National Education was obtained. Before that, the ethical approval was granted by the Gazi University Ethics Committee (265295/No. 01 dated 11.01.2022). Second, the researchers kindly invited the participants, getting their full informant consents. Third, parents whose children involved in the research were asked to submit their permissions. The privacy, confidentiality, and anonymity were considered, as well. Several codes were used for the participants (Teachers “T”, students “S”, deputies “D”, and parents “P”). No personal data was taken from the participants, and the sociodemographic characteristics are presented in percentages. Finally, no participants were forced to answer research questions.

References

- Ağalday, B., & Dağlı, A. (2019). Examining paternalistic leadership behaviours of primary school principals based on the teachers perceptions in Turkey. *Artuklu Human and Social Science Journal*, 4(2), 1-22.
- Ağaoğlu, E., Şimşek, Y., Ceylan, M., & Kesim, E. (2012). The characteristics of successful Turkish principals: Three cases. *Journal of New World Sciences Academy*, 7(2), 812-822.
- Akan, D., Yalçın, S., & Yıldırım, İ. (2014). Okul müdürü kavramına ilişkin öğretmenlerin metaforik algıları. *İlköğretim Online*, 13(1), 169-179.
- Akın-Kösterelioğlu, M. (2014). Öğretmen adaylarının okul yöneticisi kavramına ilişkin metaforik algıları. *Zeitschrift für die Welt der Türken/Journal of World of Turks*, 6(3), 115-133.
- Aktaş, T. (2019). *Okul müdürlerinin paternalistik liderlik davranışları ile politik taktikleri arasındaki ilişkiler* (Master's thesis). Pamukkale University, Turkey. Retrieved from <https://tez.yok.gov.tr/UlusalTezMerkezi/>.
- Akyol, B., & Kapçak, C. B. (2017). Pre-service teachers' perceptions of "administration" and "school principal" reflected through metaphors. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 10(3), 293-309. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1009723>.
- Allen, A. E. S. (2004). *Elementary principals' perceptions of the impact of Virginia's standards-based accountability reform initiative on their professional roles* (Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation). Virginia Commonwealth University, United States.
- Alqahtani, A. S., Noman, M., & Kaur, A. (2020). Core leadership practices of school principals in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 1-15. <https://doi.org/1741143220901857>.
- Argyropoulou, E., & Hatira, K. (2014). Metaphors and drawings as research tools of head teachers' perceptions on their management and leadership roles and responsibilities. *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, 22(4), 496-512. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2014.947832>
- Asiedu-Kumi, A. O. (2013). *Model leadership: Discovering successful principals' skills, strategies, and approaches for student success* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Southern California, USA.
- Aslan, Ş., & Özer, K. (2019). Türkiye'de kültürel liderlik bağlamında "Hulusi Kentmen" tipolojisi ve mizahi lider "Nasreddin Hoca. *Uluslararası Sosyal Bilgilerde Yeni Yaklaşımlar Dergisi (IJONASS)*, 3(2), 126-145.
- Aycan, Z. (2001). Paternalizm: Yönetim ve liderlik anlayışına ilişkin üç görgül çalışma. *Yönetim Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 1(1), 1-19.
- Aycan, Z., Kanungo, R.N. ve Mendonça, M. (2016). *Organizations and Management in Cross-Cultural Context*. (Çev. A. Kayapalı) İstanbul: KÜY.
- Aydoğdu, E. (2008). *İlköğretim okullarındaki öğrenci ve öğretmenlerin sahip oldukları okul algıları ile ideal okul algılarının metaforlar (mecazlar) yoluyla analizi*. (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Osmangazi Üniversitesi, Eskişehir.
- Balitewicz, T. F. (2015). *Principal leadership in high-achieving, high-poverty schools* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Indiana State University, USA.

- Bartell, C. A. (1989). Outstanding secondary principals reflect on instructional leadership. *The High School Journal*, 73(2), 118-128. Retrieved from <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40364672>.
- Beck, L. G., & Murphy, J. (1993). *Understanding the principalship. Metaphorical themes 1920's - 1990's*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Bennett, J. V. & Murakami, E. T. (2016). Heroic leadership redefined in the United States border context: Cases studies of successful principals in Arizona and Texas. *ISEA*, 44(1), 5-23.
- Bipath, K., & Moyo, E. (2016). Principals shaping school culture for school effectiveness in South Africa. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 48(3), 174-186. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09718923.2016.11893581>
- Bloomberg, L. D., & Volpe, M. (2008). *Completing your qualitative dissertation: A roadmap from beginning to end*. Los Angeles: SAGE.
- Bolat, T., Seymen A., O., Bolat, İ., Kinter, O. & Katı, Y. (2018). Güç mesafesi ve paternalist liderlik ilişkisi: Kuşaklar açısından bir değerlendirme. *International Social Sciences Studies Journal*, 4(25), 5496-5502.
- Bouchamma, Y. (2012). Leadership practices in effective schools in disadvantaged areas of Canada. *Education Research International*, 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/712149>
- redeson, P. V. (1987). Languages of leadership: Metaphor making in educational administration. *Administrator's Notebook*, 32(6), 1-5. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED294296.pdf>
- Brinkerhoff, R. (2003). *The success case method: Find out quickly what's working and what's not*. San Francisco: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Brookover, W. L., Beamer, L., Esthin, H., Hataway, D., Lezotte, L., Miller, S., . . . Tornetsky, L. (1982). *Creating effective schools*. Holmes Beach, FL: Learning Publications.
- Bush, T., & Glover, D. (2014). School leadership models: What do we know?. *School Leadership & Management*, 34(5), 553-571. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2014.928680>
- Cemaloğlu, N. (2005). Türkiye de okul yöneticisi yetiştirme ve istihdamı varolan durum, gelecekteki olası gelişmeler ve sorunlar. *Gazi Üniversitesi Gazi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 25(2), 249-274.
- Cerit, Y. (2008). Öğrenci, Öğretmen ve Yöneticilerin Müdür Kavramı ile İlgili Metaforlara İlişkin Görüşleri. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 33(147), 3-13.
- Çobanoğlu, N., & Gökalp, S. (2015). Öğretmen adaylarının okul müdürüne ilişkin meteforik algıları/metaphoric perceptions of teacher candidates for school managers. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 12(31), 279-295.
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Crotty, M. (1998). *The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*. London: SAGE.
- Crum, K. S., & Sherman, W. H. (2008). Facilitating high achievement: High school principals' reflections on their successful leadership practices. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 46(5), 562-580. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09578230810895492>

- Dağlı, A., & Ağalday, B. (2017). Developing a headmasters' paternalistic leadership behaviours scale in Türkiye. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(30), 190-200.
- Dağlı, A., & Ağalday, B. (2018). Okul müdürlerinin paternalist liderlik davranışlarının incelenmesi. *Elektronik Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 17(66), 518-534.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2017). Teacher education around the world: What can we learn from international practice?. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(3), 291-309. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2017.1315399>
- Day, C. (2005). Principals who sustain success: Making a difference in schools in challenging circumstances. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 8(4), 273-290. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603120500330485>
- Day, C. (2007). Sustaining success in challenging contexts: Leadership in english schools. In C. Day & K. Leithwood (Eds.), *Successful principal leadership in times of change* (pp. 59–70). Dordrecht, The Netherlands: Springer.
- Day, C. (2014). Resilient principals in challenging schools: The courage and costs of conviction. *Teachers and Teaching*, 20(5), 638-654. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2014.937959>
- Day, C. (2015). International successful school principals project (ISSPP): Multi-perspective research on school principals. Retrieved from Nottingham: University of Nottingham. https://www.uv.uio.no/ils/english/research/projects/isspp/isspp-brochure-27_jul_final_amended.pdf
- Day, C., & Leithwood, K. (Eds.). (2007). *Successful principal leadership in times of change: An international perspective*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Day, C., Gu, Q., & Sammons, P. (2016). The impact of leadership on student outcomes: How successful school leaders use transformational and instructional strategies to make a difference. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 52(2), 221-258. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X15616863>
- De Lisle, J., Annisette, S., & Bowrin-Williams, C. (2020). Leading high-poverty primary schools in Trinidad and Tobago—what do successful principals do?. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(4), 703-723. <https://doi.org/1741143219827304>.
- Dimmock, C. A., & O'Donoghue, T. A. (1997). Managerial imperatives for the improvement of school reporting to parents. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 11(4), 149-158. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513549710186254>
- Dönmez, Ö. (2008). *Türk eğitim sisteminde kullanılan yönetici metaforları* (Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Erciyes Üniversitesi, Kayseri.
- Drysdale, L., & Gurr, D. (2011). Theory and practice of successful school leadership in Australia. *School Leadership & Management*, 31(4), 355-368. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2011.606273>
- Drysdale, L., Gurr, D., & Goode, H. (2021). How successful school principals balance their leadership and management roles to make a difference. In M. Lee, K. Pollock, & P. Tulowitzki (Eds.), *How school principals use their time: Implications for school improvement, administration and leadership* (pp.126-141). London: Routledge.

- Dursun, İ. E. (2019). *Okul müdürlerinin paternalist liderlik davranışlarının okul kültürü oluşturmadaki etkisi* [The effect of paternalistic leadership behaviors of school principals on creating school culture] (Master's thesis). İstanbul Sabahattin Zaim University, İstanbul.
- Edmonds, R. (1979). Effective schools for the urban poor. *Educational Leadership*, 22, 22–23.
- Elçi, B., & Tan, Ç. (2015). Başarılı okul müdürleri arasında öğretmenlere yaklaşımları yönüyle hangi motivasyon faktörlerinin daha etkili olduğunun incelenmesi. *Journal of Computer and Education Research*, 3(6), 168-187.
- Engels, N., Hotton, G. , Devos, G. , Bouckenoghe, D. & Aelterman, A. (2008). Principals in schools with a positive school culture. *Educational Studies*, 34(3), 159-174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03055690701811263>.
- Erben, G., S., & Güneşer, A., B. (2008). The Relationship Between Paternalist Leadership and Organizational Commitment: Investigating The Role of Climate Regarding Ethics. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 82,955-968. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-007-9605-z>
- Erden, A. (2016). Proposing primary school principalship model through positive and negative metaphoric perspective. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(n12A), 71-80.
- Fennell, H. A. (1996). *An exploration of principals' metaphors for leadership and power*. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED399626.pdf> Frederickson, J. R., & Edmonds, R. R. (1979, April). Identification of instructionally effective and ineffective schools. *Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association, San Francisco, CA*.
- Fullwood, J. (2016). *Common leadership responsibilities of principals of successful turnaround model schools* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Brandman University, California.
- Garza Jr., E., Murakami-Ramvalho, E. & Merchant, B. (2011). Leadership succession and successful leadership: The case of Laura Martinez. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 10(4), 428-443. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2011.610558>.
- Giancola, J. M., & Hutchison, J. K. (2005). *Transforming the culture of school leadership: Humanizing our practice*. California: Corwin Press.
- Greenfield, T.B. (1984). Leaders and schools: Willfulness and nonnatural order in organizations. In T.J. Sergiovanni & J.E. Corbally (Eds.), *Leadership and organizational culture* (pp. 142-169). Chicago, IL: University of Illinois Press.
- Grint, K. (2005). Problems, problems, problems: The social construction of 'leadership'. *Human relations*, 58(11), 1467-1494. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726705061314>
- Gu, Q., Day, C., Walker, A., & Leithwood, K. (2018). How successful secondary school principals enact policy. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 17(3), 327-331. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2018.1496343>
- Gürbüz, R., Erdem, E., & Yıldırım, K. (2013). Başarılı okul müdürlerinin özellikleri. *Dicle Üniversitesi Ziya Gökalp Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 20, 167-179.
- Hallinger, P., & Heck, R. H. (1996). Reassessing the principal's role in school effectiveness: A review of empirical research, 1980-1995. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 32(1), 5-44. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X96032001002>

- Heffernan, A. (2019). The 'punk rock principal': A metaphor for rethinking educational leadership. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 51(2), 117-132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220620.2019.1582476>
- Heffernan, A., Netolicky, D., & Mockler, N. (2019). New and alternative metaphors for school leadership. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 51(2), 83-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220620.2019.1585768>
- Hernández-Amorós, M. J., & Martínez Ruiz, M. A. (2018). Principals' metaphors as a lens to understand how they perceive leadership. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 46(4), 602-623. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143216688470>
- Holly, M. R. (2009). *Effective leadership qualities and characteristics of urban school principals* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Robert Morris University, USA.
- Inbar, E. (1996). Free educational prison: Metaphors and images. *Educational Research*, 38(1), 77-92. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0013188960380106>
- Johnson, A. B. (2005). *The relationship between leadership behaviors of elementary principals from various school contexts and student achievement*. Argosy University/Schaumburg (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). Argosy University, Chicago.
- Kadi, A., & Beytekin, O. F. (2017). Metaphorical Perceptions of Teachers, Principals and Staff on School Management. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(15), 29-35.
- Karaçizmeli, A., & Kesken, J. (2017). 1960'lardan 2000'lere Türk sinemasında değişen patron temsilleri: Tüketim ve yönetim göstergeleri üzerinden bir analiz. *Ege Akademik Bakış*, 17(1), 127. doi:10.21121/eab.2017123472
- Karahasanoğlu, M. (2014). *İlköğretim okullarında görev yapan öğretmen algularına göre etkili okul müdürü özelliklerinin incelenmesi* (Üsküdar İlçesi Örneği). Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul.
- Kaul, V. K. (2015). *Principles and practices of management*. India: Vikas Publishing House.
- Kızıldenez, M. (2017). *Başarılı okul müdürlerinin yönetim uygulamalarının değerlendirilmesi* (Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi, Van.
- Koçak, O. (2011). *Okul müdürlerinin; öğrencilik, öğretmenlik ve müdürlük dönemlerindeki okul yöneticiliğine ilişkin metaforik alguları* (Yüksek Lisans Tezi). Gaziosmanpaşa Üniversitesi, Tokat.
- Korkmaz, M., & Çevik M. S. (2018). Ortaokul öğretmenlerinin müdür kavramına ilişkin metaforik alguları. *Kuramsal Eğitimbilim Dergisi*, 11(4), 973-1002.
- Leithwood, K., Louis, K. S., Anderson, S., & Wahlstrom, K. (2004). *How leadership influences student learning*. New York, NY: The Wallace Foundation. <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ527505>
- Leo, U., & Wickenberg, P. (2013). Professional norms in school leadership: Change efforts in implementation of education for sustainable development. *Journal of Educational Change*, 14, 403-422. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-013-9207-8>
- Lezotte, L. W. (1986). *School effectiveness: Reflections and future directions*. Paper delivered at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association. San Francisco, April.
- Likert, R. (1967). *The human organization: Its management and value*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

- Linn, G.B., Sherman, R. & Gill, P.B. (2007). Making meaning of educational leadership: the principalship in metaphor. *NASSP Bulletin*, 91(2), 161-171.
- Llorent-Bedmar, V., Cobano-Delgado, V., & Navarro-Granados, M. (2019). School leadership in disadvantaged contexts in Spain: Obstacles and improvements. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 47(1), 147-164. <https://doi.org/10.1177/174114321772808>
- Maguire, M., & Braun, A. (2019). Headship as policy narration: generating metaphors of leading in the English primary school. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 51(2), 103-116.
- Marzano, R. J., Waters, T., & McNulty, B. A. (2005). *School leadership that works: From research to results*. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development. <http://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED509055>
- Meyer, F., & Patuawa, J. (2022). Novice principals in small schools: Making sense of the challenges and contextual complexities of school leadership. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 21(2), 167-184. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2020.1757722>
- Meyers, C. V., & Hambrick Hitt, D. (2017). School turnaround principals: What does initial research literature suggest they are doing to be successful?. *Journal of Education for Students Placed at Risk (JESPAR)*, 22(1), 38-56.
- Monroe, C. E. S. (2003). *An analysis of principalship metaphors at the beginning of the new millennium* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of North Carolina, Greensboro
- Moral, C., Martín-Romera, A., Martínez-Valdivia, E., & Olmo-Extremera, M. (2018). Successful secondary school principalship in disadvantaged contexts from a leadership for learning perspective. *School Leadership & Management*, 38(1), 32-52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2017.1358161>
- Murakami, E. T. & Orr, M. T. (2012). International successful school principal project: Cases of improvement and sustainability in North American Schools. *Journal of Cases in Educational Leadership*, 15(3) 3–6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1555458912447795>.
- Naidoo, B. & Perumal, J. (2014). Female principals leading at disadvantaged schools in Johannesburg, South Africa. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(6) 808–824. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143214543202>.
- Nichols, S., Glass, G., & Berliner, D. (2012). High-stakes testing and student achievement: Updated analyses with NAEP data. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 20, 1-35 <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.v20n20.2012>
- Noman, M., Awang Hashim, R., & Abdullah, S. (2018). Contextual leadership practices: The case of a successful school principal in Malaysia. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 46(3), 474-490. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143216665840>
- Örücü, D. (2014). Öğretmen adaylarının okul, okul yönetimi ve Türk eğitim sistemine yönelik metaforik algıları. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 20(3), 327-358. <https://doi.org/10.14527/kuey.2014.014>
- Özgenel, M. & Gökçe, B. D. (2019). Metaphorical analysis of the perceptions of the primary school students on the concepts of school, teacher and principal. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 11(1), 100-122.

- Parylo, O., & Zepeda, S. J. (2014). Describing an 'effective' principal: Perceptions of the central office leaders. *School Leadership and Management: Formerly School Organization*, 34(5), 518-537. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2014.928684>
- Payne, G., & Williams, M. (2005). Generalization in qualitative research. *Sociology*, 39(2), 295-314. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038505050540>
- Pesen, A., & Kara, İ. & Gedik, M. (2015). Çocuk gelişimi bölümü 2. sınıf öğrencilerinin “müdür” kavramına ilişkin metafor algıları. *Siirt Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 4, 39-61.
- Reid, D. B. (2021). US principals' sensemaking of the future roles and responsibilities of school principals. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 49(2), 251-267. <https://doi.org/10.1741143219896072>.
- Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., McNaughton, N.C., & Ormston, R. (2014). *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Robinson, V., Lloyd, C., & Rowe, K. (2008). The impact of leadership on student outcomes: An analysis of the differential effects of leadership types. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 44(5), 635-674. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X08321509>.
- Samier, E. A. (2019). The theory and uses of metaphor in educational administration and leadership: a rejoinder. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 51(2), 182-195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220620.2019.1596889>
- Santaella, C. M. (2018). A comparative study of the professional identity of two secondary school principals in disadvantaged contexts. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 19(2), 145-170. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2018.1513152>.
- Seidman, I. (2006). *Interviewing as qualitative research: A guide for researchers in education and the social sciences*. London: Teachers College Press.
- Steyn, G. M. (2014). Exploring successful principalship in South Africa: A case study. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, 49(3) 347-361. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0021909613486621>.
- Tan, C. Y., & Dimmock, C. (2014). How a 'top-performing' Asian school system formulates and implements policy: the case of Singapore. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(5), 743-763. <https://doi.org/10.1177/174114321351050>
- Todd, Z., & Harrison, S. J. (2008). Metaphor analysis. In S. N. Hesse-Biber & P. Leavy (Eds.), *Handbook of Emergent Methods* (pp. 479-93). New York: Guilford
- Trancevic, A. & Vaupot, S. R. (2009). Exploring aspiring principals' perceptions of principalship: A Slovenian case study. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 37(1) 85-105. doi: 10.1177/1741143208099331.
- Tubin, D. (2017). Leadership identity construction practices: The case of successful Israeli school principals. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 45(5) 790-805. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143216682503>.
- Turhan, M., & Yaraş, Z. (2013). Öğretmen ve öğrencilerin öğretmen, disiplin, müdür, sınıf kuralları, ödül ve ceza kavramlarına ilişkin metafor algıları. *Fırat Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 23(1), 129-145

- Tüzel, E. & Şahin, D., (2014). İlköğretim birinci kademe öğrencilerinin okul yöneticilerine ilişkin metaforları. *Adıyaman Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (17), 355-396. <https://doi.org/10.14520/adyusbd.736>
- Tvnavcevic, A., & Vaupot, S. R. (2009). Exploring aspiring principals' perceptions of principalship: A Slovenian case. *Educational Management Administration and Leadership*, 37(1), 85-105. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143208099331>
- Uğurluoglu, O., Aldogan, E. U., Turgut, M., & Ozatkan, Y. (2018). The effect of paternalistic leadership on job performance and intention to leave the job. *Journal of Health Management*, 20(1), 46-55.
- Wildy, H. (2003). Meaning and method: Using metaphors in qualitative research. In T. A. O'Donoghue, & K. Punch (Eds.), *Qualitative educational research in action* (pp. 121-135). London: Routledge.
- Wong, C. S., & Law, K. S. (2017). The effects of leader and follower emotional intelligence on performance and attitude: An exploratory study. In C. Wong & K. S. Law (Eds.), *Leadership perspectives* (pp. 97-128). London: Routledge.
- Yalçın, M., & Erginer, A. (2012). İlköğretim okullarında okul müdürüne ilişkin metaforik algılar. *Öğretmen Eğitimi ve Eğitimcileri Dergisi*, 1(2), 229-256.
- Yalçın, M., & Erginer, A. (2014). İlköğretim okulu öğrencilerinin okul müdürü algılarına ilişkin yaptıkları çizimler. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 39(171), 270-285.
- Yin, R. K. (2016). *Qualitative research from start to finish*. New York: Guilford Press.
- Ylimaki, R. M., L. Jacobson, S. L. & Drysdale, L. (2007). Making a difference in challenging, high-poverty schools: Successful principals in the USA, England, and Australia. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 18(4), 361-381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450701712486>.
- Zembat, R., Tunçeli, H. İ., & Akşin, E. (2015). Okul Öncesi öğretmen adaylarının "okul yöneticisi" kavramına ilişkin algılarına yönelik metafor çalışması. *Hacettepe University Faculty of Health Sciences Journal*, 1, 446-459.